

Bridging the Gap between Real-World and Formal Binary Lifting through Filtered-Simulation (Extended Report)

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Binary lifting is a key component in binary analysis tools. In order to guarantee the correctness of binary lifting, researchers have proposed various formally verified lifters. However, such formally verified lifters have too strict requirements on binary, which do not sufficiently reflect real-world lifters. In addition, real-world lifters use heuristic-based assumptions to lift binary code, which makes it difficult to guarantee the correctness of the lifted code using formal methods. In this paper, we propose a new interpretation of the correctness of real-world binary lifting. We formalize the process of binary lifting with heuristic-based assumptions used in real-world lifters by dividing it into a series of transformations, where each transformation represents a lift with new abstraction features. We define the correctness of each transformation as *filtered-simulation*, which is a variant of bi-simulation, between programs before and after transformation. We present three essential transformations in binary lifting and formalize them: (1) control flow graph reconstruction, (2) abstract stack reconstruction, and (3) function input/output identification. We implement our approach for x86-64 Linux binaries, named FIBLE, and demonstrate that it can correctly lift Coreutils and CGC datasets compiled with GCC.

CCS Concepts: • **Security and privacy** → **Software reverse engineering**; • **Theory of computation** → **Program semantics**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Binary lifting, formal semantics

1 Introduction

Binary analysis is essential for analyzing programs that do not have source code, such as COTS (Commercial Off-The-Shelf) software, malware, and legacy software. By using binary analysis, one can build a variety of techniques on programs without source code, including vulnerability analysis [14], malware detection [15], binary rewriting, optimization [20], and more.

Binary analysis frameworks offer a set of tools and techniques for analyzing binary code. Most of these frameworks utilize Intermediate Representations (IRs) that are well-suited for binary code analysis. They provide various high-level abstractions that are not inherently present in the binary code, such as Control Flow Graphs (CFGs), functions, and global/local variables. These abstractions enable developers to design precise and efficient analysis tools [6, 38].

In this paper, we define *binary lifting* as the process of generating IRs from binary code while preserving the program’s semantics. We refer to *decompilation* as the process of generating human-readable source code, with a focus on readability over correctness. Several tools are available for binary lifting (e.g., McSema [22], RetDec [7]) and decompilation (e.g., Ghidra [2], IDA Pro [49]), with many decompilers integrating their own lifter and IR, such as Ghidra’s P-Code [3] and IDA’s Microcode [50].

Ensuring the correctness of binary lifting is critical for constructing IRs that provide useful abstractions for precise and efficient analysis. Many existing binary analysis tools and techniques [28, 35, 39, 57, 58] rely on the accuracy of underlying binary lifters, and inaccuracies can lead to erroneous analysis outcomes. An empirical study by Liu et al. [38] demonstrates that the correctness of binary lifting is a significant factor in the accuracy of binary analysis tools.

To ensure the correctness of binary lifting, researchers have proposed various formal methods that guarantee an overapproximation of the behavior of binary code. As is well known, overapproximation includes all behaviors of the analysis target, while underapproximation captures only their subset. For example, Verbeek et al. [55] proposed provably overapproximative CFG reconstruction of C-compiled x86-64 binaries. Similarly, Dasgupta et al. [18] proposed scalable validation of binary lifting by combining instruction-wise validation. They ensure that their CFG reconstruction and instruction-wise lifting of binary code preserves the same behavior as the original binary code when successfully analyzing all possible control flows with all possible inputs.

However, there is a significant gap between real-world lifters and formally verified lifters. Since analyzing all control flows is impractical, real-world lifters use “assumptions” to introduce abstractions, intentionally underapproximating binary behavior to make lifting feasible. For example, when reconstructing stack variables, they assume that the stack frame pointer is not corrupted after a call instruction, rather than analyzing all possible control flows within the callee function. These assumptions are typically based on developer heuristics, which are often undocumented and informal, making it difficult to define and verify the correctness of real-world lifters.

To bridge this gap, we propose a new interpretation of the correctness of real-world binary lifting. We first define the correctness of real-world lifting as *filtered-simulation*, a variant of bi-simulation, between programs before and after transformation. Our method guarantees correctness while also supporting realistic analyses, similar to real-world lifters. This approach distinguishes between translation errors, caused by bugs in the lifter, and assumption violations, which result from intentional underapproximations.

We apply our method to three key transformations in binary lifting: (1) CFG reconstruction, (2) abstract stack reconstruction, and (3) function input/output identification. For each, we formalize assumptions and provide a proof sketch of correctness. These transformations are crucial for *function reconstruction*, enabling modular analysis in binary analysis.

We implement a prototype named FIBLE (**F**iltered **B**inary **L**ifting and **E**xecution tool) to lift x86-64 Linux binaries and evaluate it on 37 binaries from the Coreutils and 44 binaries from the CGC datasets [27], compiled with GCC. Our approach achieves results comparable to real-world binary lifters while providing formal guarantees. In contrast, existing formal methods fail to lift nearly half of the CGC dataset and are, on average, 16.8 times slower due to their stricter requirements.

To summarize, we present a novel approach to designing a correct yet practical binary lifter by composing a series of correct transformations. The technical contributions include the following:

- We define the correctness of binary lifting as *filtered-simulation*, a variant of bi-simulation, between programs before and after transformation.
- We present three essential transformations to reconstruct function abstractions in binary lifting and formalize them: CFG reconstruction, abstract stack reconstruction, and function input/output identification.
- We implement our approach for x86-64 Linux binaries and demonstrate that it can correctly lift binaries from the Coreutils and CGC datasets.

2 Motivating Example

We present a motivating example to illustrate the limitations of existing binary lifting frameworks (both formal and real-world) and the need for our proposed framework. We use C code as a representative of its compiled binary code.

Figures 1a to 1c present three C functions, `f`, `g`, and `h`, respectively. Both `f` and `g` return their input value if it is in the range `[0, 1]`. If the input value is out of the range, `f` returns 1 while `g` behaves as undefined (**undef**) because accessing `arr[i]` causes an out-of-bounds write. The function

```

1 int f(int i) {
2   int arr[2] = {1,};
3   if (0 <= i && i < 2)
4     arr[i] = 0;
5   return arr[0];
6 }

```

(a) Well-defined code

```

1 int g(int i) {
2   int arr[2] = {1,};
3   arr[i] = 0;
4   return arr[0];
5 }

```

(b) Real-world code

```

1 int h(int i) {
2   int arr[2] = {1,};
3   arr[i] = 0;
4   asm("lea %, %rbp"
5     :: "m"(backdoor));
6   return arr[0];
7 }

```

(c) Ill-defined code

Approach	Lifting result		
	f	g	h
Overapproximative lifter	F	X	X
Real-world lifter	F	G	G
Our proposed lifter	F	G	H

X = Fail to lift
F(i) = if $0 \leq i \leq 1$ then i else 1
G(i) = if $0 \leq i \leq 1$ then i else **undef**
H(i) = **undef**

Fig. 1. (above) Three C functions, f, g, and h
 (below) Results of overapproximative, real-world, and our proposed lifters

h is the same as g except it has additional assembly code at lines 4–5, which corrupts the x86-64 frame pointer register rbp. This is a way to implant a backdoor in the binary using return-oriented programming (ROP) [12, 46, 51]. As the actual lifted code is not important for this example, we only include the semantics of the lifted code for the compiled functions, denoted as F , G , and H .

In the following, we discuss the limitations of existing binary lifting frameworks and how our proposed framework can address them.

Overapproximative Lifting. Formal methods for binary lifting are overapproximative by design, making them fail to lift real-world binaries. For example, the formal lifter by Verbeek et al. [55] can lift binary code only if the lifted code can have the same semantics as the original binary for all possible inputs. Thus, the lifting of f in Figure 1a would succeed because the behavior of f is known for all inputs.

However, this requirement could be too strict for real-world binaries. Real-world binaries often contain legitimate yet undefined behaviors (e.g., missing checks for trustworthy inputs) and possess several paths, making it generally undecidable to verify the requirement. For example, the lifting of g in Figure 1b would fail because i is not known to be in the range $[0, 1]$.

Real-world Binary Lifting. On the other hand, real-world binary lifters are permissive to support as many binaries as possible. This can lead to analyses or assumptions that are generally applicable but incorrect in special cases. For example, such a lifter might successfully lift g by assuming that the function will not cause a buffer overflow, but incorrectly lift h by incorrectly assuming that the saved stack pointer will not be modified. We tested this code with two popular binary lifters, IDA-Pro and Ghidra, and validated that they both lift h incorrectly.

A more serious problem is that real-world lifters are not formalized, making it difficult to reason about incorrect results. In general, the cause of incorrect results can be attributed to incorrect analysis or violated assumptions. Because real-world lifters embed their assumptions in their implementations, it is difficult to identify why their analysis does not work as expected. Therefore, their results are untrustworthy, and any analysis built on top of them is also untrustworthy.

Our Solution. We propose a binary lifting framework that is both permissive and formalized. The key concept is to lift binaries under certain conditions, which we refer to as *assumptions*. These assumptions specify how the lower-level language is expected to behave when represented in the higher-level language.

Fig. 2. Overview of the proposed framework. Dashed lines indicate transformations using assumptive analysis.

To ensure the correctness of the lifted code under certain assumptions, we introduce the concept of *filtered-simulation*. For example, in the case of function g , we assume the saved stack pointer rbp remains unchanged after accessing $arr[i]$. If this assumption is violated, the program’s behavior is considered *undefined*. Thus, the result is undefined for g when the input value is out of the range $[0, 1]$. Similarly, for function h , the result is undefined for all inputs.

The key advantage of our framework is that it allows reasoning about binary code via the lifted code, whether the code is fully or partially defined. For instance, with function f , one can verify that no assumption violations occur for any input, similar to an over-approximative lifter. Even when the lifted code contains undefined behavior (due to assumption violations), as in g , formal methods can still be applied to analyze the well-defined parts of the code. Exploring partial behavior remains valuable for many applications, such as concolic testing, fuzzing, and under-approximative analysis tasks. Our framework guarantees that valid execution traces of the lifted code always align with the behavior of the original binary.

Thus, our framework can lift a wider range of binaries while ensuring correctness.

3 Approach

This section provides existing real-world binary lifting techniques and our approach to formalizing binary lifting.

3.1 Real-world binary lifting

To understand how real-world lifters work, we have examined the source code of existing binary lifting frameworks: BAP [13], Angr [52], radare2 [47], BINSEC [23], etc. Their lifting consists of two steps: instruction-level lifting and transformations. First, the lifters transform the input assembly code to an instruction-level IR. Then, they apply a series of transformations to refine the transformation results in IR and recover abstractions.

Assumptive analysis. The lifters use two types of transformations: standard and *assumptive*. Standard transformations use traditional compiler optimization techniques such as constant propagation, dead code elimination, and common subexpression elimination. These transformations typically have a strong theoretical foundation for their correctness [10, 11, 24, 31–33]. On the other hand, certain transformations are specialized for binary lifting such as symbolization, abstract stack reconstruction, and function input/output identification. We observed that these transformations rely on certain “assumptions” about the input binary (e.g., the presence of specific data structures for control flow, stack, and function calls). These assumptions combine well-founded principles with optimistic guesses. For example, assuming the stack frame pointer remains intact and inferring registers from calling conventions are standard compiler principles, whereas assuming a jump is intra-procedural or a tail call relies on heuristics and compiler-specific optimizations. We refer to this type of analysis as *assumptive analysis*. In this paper, we focus on three types of assumptive analysis and their corresponding transformations: *CFG reconstruction*, *abstract stack reconstruction*, and *function input/output identification*.

Limitations in formalization. Existing binary lifters hinder formalization by not explicitly declaring assumptions or syntax changes at each step. Some features appear only after specific transformations, yet lifters often include all features in the IR from the start. Since each transformation introduces new features to the lifted code, incrementally adding features to the IR syntax simplifies formalization.

3.2 Overview of our approach

We formalize our approach using four IRs for each transformation of the lifting process: *Instruction-Level IR (ILIR)*, *Flow-Graph IR (FGIR)*, *Abstract-Stack IR (ASIR)*, and *Input-Output IR (IOIR)*. We summarize their definitions in §5.1, 5.2, 6.1 and 7.1, respectively:

- ILIR represents the most lightweight IR, closely mirroring assembly code, as seen in frameworks like Remill [37].
- FGIR is a CFG-based IR that uses only registers, without variables, as seen in tools like BAP, Angr, radare2, and BINSEC.
- ASIR includes local variables and stack frames. While many lifters use these features as data structures or annotations, they often do not exist as a separate IR.
- IOIR incorporates function signatures similar to RetDec [7], McSema [22], Ghidra P-Code, and IDA Microcode, but excludes type and symbol information.

These IRs capture key stages of the binary lifting process. Formalizing both intermediate and final IRs is crucial for representing real-world lifters across various levels of abstraction.

Our approach formally defines binary lifting and proves its correctness. As illustrated in Figure 2, we divide the lifting process into several stages, with each stage representing a transformation between two programs in different languages. Dashed lines indicate transformations using assumptive analysis, while solid lines represent standard transformations. The program before the transformation is referred to as the low-level program, and the one after is the high-level program.

Importantly, these terms are relative to the transformation and do not necessarily refer to assembly and high-level languages like C. Instead, they represent different levels of abstraction within the binary lifting process. Aside from newly introduced language features, the low-level and high-level languages share the same syntactic elements. For each transformation, we define and prove its correctness. The overall correctness of the lifting is determined by the correctness of the transformations at each individual stage.

We define a language L as a quadruple $(\mathbb{P}, \Sigma, f^{\text{init}}, \rightsquigarrow)$ consisting of a set of programs \mathbb{P} , a set of states Σ , an initial state function f^{init} , and a step relation \rightsquigarrow . A program $p \in \mathbb{P}$ represents a syntactic element of the language. A state $\sigma \in \Sigma$ represents information about the execution of a program at a certain point. The initial state function $f^{\text{init}} : \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(\Sigma)$ represents the set of possible states at the start of a given program. The step relation $\rightsquigarrow \subseteq (\mathbb{P} \times \Sigma \times \Sigma)$ represents a relation that, given a program and a state, indicates what state can be after a single transition. The execution of a program is the process of starting from the program’s initial state and modifying the states according to the step relation. The sequence of states passed during the execution of a program is called a trace and is denoted as τ . The set of all possible traces of a program is denoted as \mathbb{T} . We denote $\tau \cdot \sigma$ as appending a state to the end of a trace.

For each stage, the transformation and its correctness definition and proof have a similar structure.

Transformation. A transformation consists of a static analysis \mathcal{A} and a syntactic transformation \mathcal{T} . It takes a low-level program p_L and produces a high-level program p_H and assumptions H .

Assumptions are information about high-level program features that cannot be determined by analyzing low-level programs alone. For example, a low-level program might not indicate whether a particular jump is a function call or a return, while the high-level language distinguishes between

$$\begin{array}{l}
p_{IL} = \left[\begin{array}{l} 0 \mapsto \mathbf{jmp} \ 8, \\ 1 \mapsto \mathbf{assign} \ r_2 \ 3, \\ 2 \mapsto \mathbf{jmp} \ r_2, \\ 3 \mapsto \mathbf{assign} \ r_2 \ 1, \\ 4 \mapsto \mathbf{jmp} \ r_3, \\ 8 \mapsto \mathbf{jmp} \ r_1 \end{array} \right], [0, 8] \\
p_{FG} = \mathbf{func} \ 0 \ [(0, \mathbf{call?} \ 8 \ 1), \\ \quad (1, \mathbf{fallthrough} \ (\mathbf{assign} \ r_2 \ 3) \ 2), \\ \quad (2, \mathbf{goto_ind} \ r_2 \ [3]), \\ \quad (3, \mathbf{fallthrough} \ (\mathbf{assign} \ r_2 \ 1) \ 4), \\ \quad (4, \mathbf{ret?} \ r_3)], \\ \mathbf{func} \ 8 \ [(8, \mathbf{ret?} \ r_1)]
\end{array}$$

$$\mathcal{A}(p_{IL}) = (H, \hat{a}) \text{ where } H = \begin{cases} 0 \rightarrow \text{Call} \\ 2 \rightarrow \text{Jmp} \\ 4 \rightarrow \text{Ret} \\ 8 \rightarrow \text{Ret} \end{cases} \quad \hat{a} = [(0, [(1, 2), (2, 3), (3, 4)]), (8, [])]$$

Fig. 3. CFG reconstruction from ILIR to FGIR of an example program

the two. In such cases, static analysis introduces an assumption about whether the jump is a call or a return, and the transformation constructs a high-level program based on that assumption.

The first step, static analysis \mathcal{A} , takes a low-level program p_L and produces assumptions H and an analysis result \hat{a} for the executions that satisfy those assumptions.

For CFG reconstruction, which takes an ILIR program as input, the assumptions pertain to the types of jumps (e.g., jump, call, return) for each jump instruction. For abstract stack reconstruction, the assumptions involve the stack frame size and stack pointer manipulation after indirect calls. For function input/output identification, the assumptions concern the used/defined registers in indirect calls.

Unlike traditional static analysis, which analyzes all the executions of a low-level program, our static analysis analyzes only the executions that are valid for the low-level program's corresponding high-level program. It infers necessary information to construct the high-level program as assumptions.

The second step, syntactic transformation \mathcal{T} , takes the low-level program p_L , assumptions H , and the analysis result \hat{a} to produce the high-level program p_H . Syntactic transformation simply translates the given assumptions and analysis results into the syntax of the high-level language.

Definition of Correctness. The correctness of the transformation between low-level and high-level programs is defined using two relations: simulation relation \sim and filtering relation \triangleright .

We first define a simulation relation $\sim \subseteq \mathcal{P}(\Sigma_L \times \Sigma_H)$ between the states of the low-level and high-level languages. It represents the correspondence between the states of the low-level and high-level programs.

Next, we define a filtering relation $\triangleright \subseteq \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{H} \times \mathbb{P}_L \times \mathbb{T}_L \times \mathbb{T}_H)$, that checks whether the execution of the low-level program satisfies the constraints of the corresponding high-level language features. Since certain high-level features cannot be inferred directly from the low-level program, the filtering relation relies on assumptions. For instance, it aligns a low-level trace with a high-level trace based on assumptions about whether jumps represent function calls or returns. Importantly, the filtering relation remains valid even if these assumptions are violated during execution, leading to an undefined state.

Given the filtering relation, we propose a filtered-simulation (definition 4.3) as a definition of the correspondence between the low-level and high-level programs. We define a transformation as correct if the low-level program and the high-level program with the assumptions generated by the transformation satisfy the filtered-simulation.

Proof of Correctness. We prove the correctness of the transformation in two steps.

The first step is to prove that the static analysis is sound. The soundness of the analysis means that the assumptions and the analysis results produced by the analysis represent all possible traces of the high-level language that correspond to the low-level language with the filtering relation for the assumptions. To clearly express this, we introduce a concretization function, γ , which maps a static analysis result, \hat{a} , to a set of all possible high-level language traces that correspond to the low-level language traces with the filtering relation. The goal is to prove that $\gamma(\hat{a})$ represents all possible traces of the high-level language that correspond to the filtering relation for the assumptions.

The second step focuses on the syntactic transformation's correctness when the static analysis is sound. We first break down the correctness into more manageable, specific criteria. Then, we verify each criterion individually as outlined in theorem 4.11. The goal is to prove that the transformation satisfies each condition of theorem 4.11.

Example. Figure 3 shows an example ILIR program p_{IL} , its static analysis result $\mathcal{A}(p_{IL})$, and the result of its syntactic transformation $p_{FG} = \mathcal{T}(p_{IL}, H, \hat{a})$, which is an FGIR program. In this example, low-level language is ILIR and high-level language is FGIR.

The low-level program p_{IL} is represented as a map from addresses to instructions and two entry points $[0, 8]$, which are the start addresses of the program. The program has only three kinds of instructions: **jmp** w is an unconditional jump, which jumps to the address w , **jmp** r is an indirect jump to the address stored in the register r , and **assign** r w is an assignment of the constant word w to the register r and jumps to the instruction at the next address.

The static analysis $\mathcal{A}(p_{IL})$ analyzes the low-level program p_{IL} and produces assumptions H and an analysis result \hat{a} . The assumptions H is a map from addresses of jump instructions to the role of the jump. For example, $(0 \rightarrow \text{Call})$ means that the jump at address 0 is a function call, and it should return to the next address 1. Similarly, **Ret** means that the jump is a return, and the jump address should be matched with the assumed return address at the call site. **Jmp** means that the jump is an intra-procedural jump. This judgment is heuristic, mostly based on the syntactic pattern of instructions (i.e. used register, function epilogue pattern, etc.).

The analysis result \hat{a} is a list of pairs, each pair contains the address of an entry point and a collection of possible intra-procedural jumps from the entry point when the assumptions are satisfied. For example, $(0, [(1, 2), (2, 3), (3, 4)])$ in analysis result \hat{a} indicates that when the program is started from address 0, the state at address 2 can jump only to 3 when all assumptions are satisfied during the execution. We consider all non-jump instructions as a part of the intra-procedural jump which targets the next address. The analysis result at address 8 is empty, which means that no intra-procedural jumps start from address 8.

Using the assumptions H and the analysis result \hat{a} , the syntactic transformation $\mathcal{T}(p_{IL}, H, \hat{a})$ produces a high-level program. The high-level program consists of two functions, **func** 0 and **func** 8. In this program, the role of the jump instruction is explicitly defined. For example, $(0, \text{call? } 8 \ 1)$ means that the jump at address 0 is a call and should return to the address 1. Also, an indirect jump target is explicitly bound to the set of possible targets. For example, $(2, \text{goto_ind } r_2 \ [3])$ means that the jump at address 2 is an indirect jump, and the target is one of the elements in the set $\{3\}$.

Now, we explain how the correctness of the transformation is defined and satisfied in this example. Our definition of the correctness is based on the simulation relation \sim and the filtering relation \triangleright with the assumptions H . To explain these components clearly, we consider two possible traces of the low-level program in Figure 3 and its related high-level traces by the filtering relation as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4a shows two possible traces of the low-level program. A node represents the address of an instruction, and a path represents a trace of the program. The blue solid trace is the one

Using this filtering relation, we can define the filtered-simulation with a low-level program and a high-level program. When a low-level trace and a high-level trace have the same length and their corresponding states are in the simulation relation, they satisfy the following two properties. The first property is that if the high-level trace extends to contain the next state, then the low-level trace can step forward to the next state and two states are in the simulation relation. For example, the single-length trace $(8, \Gamma_{b0}, 8, \delta_1)$ in the high-level program p_{FG} can step forward to the next state $(1, \Gamma_{b0}, 0, \delta_0)$. It means that the corresponding single-length low-level trace $(8, \Gamma_{b0})$ in the low-level program p_{LL} should step forward to the next state $(1, \Gamma_{b0})$ and the next state is in the simulation relation. Note that the first property does not require the filtering relation. The second property is that if the low-level trace extends to include the next state and it has a filtering relation with any high-level trace, then the high-level trace can step forward to the next state and two states are in the simulation relation. For example, a sub-trace of the blue solid trace in Figure 4b $(0, \Gamma_{b0}, 0, \delta_0) \rightsquigarrow \dots \rightsquigarrow (2, \Gamma_{b1}, 0, \delta_0)$ can step forward to the next state and the extended trace also has a filtering relation with a sub-trace of Figure 4c. Note that requiring the filtering relation in this property enables p_{FG} to only represent the blue solid trace, not the red dashed trace that jumps from address 2 to 1 (which cannot be represented by `goto_ind` r_2 [3] because it only allows to jump to 3). The red dashed trace illustrates that even if assumptions are violated during execution, the filtering relation still holds, ensuring that the translation remains correct.

4 Formalization

In this section, we present formalization of our approach by formally defining a transformation and its correctness and proving the correctness.

4.1 Transformation

Given two languages L_L and L_H , we define the set of states of the languages as Σ_L and Σ_H , and the set of traces of the languages as \mathbb{T}_L and \mathbb{T}_H , respectively. A trace is a sequence of states. We define step relations \rightsquigarrow_L and \rightsquigarrow_H to represent state transitions. A trace $\tau_L \in \mathbb{T}_L$ is valid for a program p_L if it follows the step relation. Specifically, τ_L is valid if and only if $p_L \vdash \sigma_L \rightsquigarrow_L \sigma'_L$ holds for every $(\sigma_L, \sigma'_L) \in \tau_L$.

Definition 4.1 (Valid trace). A trace τ_L is a valid trace of p_L if $p_L \vdash \sigma_L \rightsquigarrow_L \sigma'_L$ for all $(\sigma_L, \sigma'_L) \in \tau_L$. We denote it as $p_L \vdash \tau_L$.

We write assumptions $H \in \mathcal{H}$ for a low-level language L_L and its high-level language L_H . For a low-level program p_L , we denote a filtering relation between a trace of the low-level language τ_L and a trace of the high-level language τ_H with given assumptions H as $H, p_L \vdash \tau_L \supseteq \tau_H$. In later sections, we define the filtering relation for each lifting stage, which satisfies the following properties.

Definition 4.2 (Filtering condition). A relation \supseteq between languages L_L and L_H satisfies the filtering condition if it has the following properties for all H, p_L, τ_L , and τ_H :

- $(H, p_L \vdash \tau_L \supseteq \tau_H) \Rightarrow p_L \vdash \tau_L$.
- $(H, p_L \vdash \tau_L \supseteq \tau_H) \Rightarrow \text{length}(\tau_L) = \text{length}(\tau_H)$
- $(H, p_L \vdash \tau_L \supseteq \tau_H) \Rightarrow (H, p_L \vdash \tau'_L \supseteq \tau'_H)$ for all τ'_L and τ'_H which are prefixes of τ_L and τ_H , respectively, of the same length.

A static analysis \mathcal{A} is a function that takes a low-level program p_L and returns assumptions and an abstraction: $\mathcal{A}(p_L) = (H, \hat{a})$. The abstraction \hat{a} represents a set of possible traces of the high-level language with the assumptions H .

A transformation \mathcal{T} is a function that takes a low-level program p_L , assumptions H , and an abstraction \hat{a} and returns a high-level program p_H : $\mathcal{T}(p_L, H, \hat{a}) = p_H$.

4.2 Correctness of Transformation

The strongest notion of program equivalence is *bi-simulation* [31, 34], which ensures two program states remain related after each execution step. However, it is unsuitable for binary lifting because some low-level behaviors, such as arbitrary stack pointer modifications, may not have corresponding high-level behaviors.

A weaker approach, *backward-simulation* [34], preserves the relation only for steps of the high-level program. Although it could be applied in binary lifting, it does not fully capture low-level semantics. For example, using backward-simulation for CFG reconstruction does not ensure that the control flows of the high-level program align exactly with those of the low-level program.

Forward simulation, on the other hand, preserves the relation for low-level program steps but shares similar limitations with bi-simulation: some low-level behaviors may not have equivalents in high-level languages. Additionally, it may introduce behaviors in the high-level program that do not exist in the low-level program. This makes it unsuitable for binary lifting, which requires the high-level program to precisely represent only the behaviors of the low-level program, without adding any extra behaviors.

Thus, we propose a new notion of equivalence called *filtered-simulation*. Filtered-simulation is in between of bi-simulation and backward-simulation. It subsumes backward-simulation in the sense that if two programs satisfy filtered-simulation, then they satisfy backward-simulation. Moreover, for a low-level program, if its trace satisfies the filtering relation, then the trace after one step is related to the trace after one step of its high-level program. Filtered-simulation captures that the behavior of a high-level language is the only possible behavior of a low-level language that meets the assumptions. In addition, if assumptions are precise enough to capture all traces of a low-level language, then filtered-simulation is equivalent to bi-simulation.

We first define the relation $\sim \subseteq \mathcal{P}(\Sigma_L \times \Sigma_H)$ as a relation between the states of two languages L_L and L_H . For simplicity, we use a notation $\tau_L \sim \tau_H$ to denote that the relation \sim holds for all corresponding states in the traces τ_L and τ_H , and the lengths of two traces are the same.

Definition 4.3 (Filtered-simulation). A relation \sim is filtered-simulation from p_L to p_H with respect to a filtering relation \supseteq and assumptions H if and only if for all τ_L and τ_H ,

- $\forall \sigma_H. (p_L \vdash \tau_L) \wedge (p_H \vdash \tau_H \cdot \sigma_H) \wedge (\tau_L \sim \tau_H) \Rightarrow \exists \sigma_L. (p_L \vdash \tau_L \cdot \sigma_L) \wedge (\sigma_L \sim \sigma_H)$
- $\forall \sigma_L, \tau'_H. (H, p_L \vdash \tau_L \cdot \sigma_L \supseteq \tau'_H) \wedge (p_H \vdash \tau_H) \wedge (\tau_L \sim \tau_H) \Rightarrow \exists \sigma_H. (p_H \vdash \tau_H \cdot \sigma_H) \wedge (\sigma_L \sim \sigma_H)$

In the definition of filtered-simulation, we restrict the two programs to follow the same number of steps, similar to lock-step simulation [34], for simplicity. While this prevents us from defining transformations that change trace length, it is sufficient for our purposes since our transformations do not alter trace length. Additionally, our approach can easily be combined with classical optimization passes, such as dead code elimination, which modify trace length but do not require filtered-simulation and can be verified separately.

The only difference between filtered-simulation and bi-simulation is that filtered-simulation can ignore the behaviors of a low-level language that are not defined in a high-level language. The next theorem states that if assumptions are precise enough to capture all traces of a low-level language, then filtered-simulation is equivalent to bi-simulation.

THEOREM 4.4 (BI-SIMULATION FOR MOST PRECISE ASSUMPTIONS). *For a filtered-simulation \sim from p_L to p_H with respect to a filtering relation \supseteq and assumptions H , τ_L , and τ_H , if the following holds:*

$$(p_L \vdash \tau_L) \Rightarrow \exists \tau'_H. (H, p_L \vdash \tau_L \supseteq \tau'_H),$$

then $\forall \sigma_L. (p_L \vdash \tau_L \cdot \sigma_L) \wedge (p_H \vdash \tau_H) \wedge (\tau_L \sim \tau_H) \Rightarrow \exists \sigma_H. (p_H \vdash \tau_H \cdot \sigma_H) \wedge (\sigma_L \sim \sigma_H)$ holds.

Fig. 5. Single stage of the binary lifting process

A transformation uses a static analysis result \hat{a} to ensure the properties of a high-level program. We use the concretization function γ to convert the abstraction to the set of traces of the high-level program. We define a sound abstraction for a filtering relation \supseteq and assumptions H as follows:

Definition 4.5 (Sound abstraction). An abstraction \hat{a} is sound for a filtering relation \supseteq , assumptions H , and a program p_L if and only if for all τ_L and τ_H , $(H, p_L \vdash \tau_L \supseteq \tau_H \Rightarrow \tau_H \in \gamma(\hat{a}))$.

A transformation \mathcal{T} has three inputs: a low-level program p_L , assumptions H , and an abstraction \hat{a} . We define the correctness of a transformation as follows:

PROPOSITION 4.6 (CORRECTNESS OF TRANSFORMATION). *A transformation \mathcal{T} is correct if and only if for all p_L , H , and \hat{a} , if \hat{a} is sound for a filtering relation \supseteq , assumptions H , and a program p_L , then \sim is a filtered-simulation from p_L to $\mathcal{T}(p_L, H, \hat{a})$.*

Now, we can transform a low-level program to a high-level program in two steps:

- (1) Analyze a low-level program p_L using a static analysis \mathcal{A} and generate assumptions H and a sound abstraction \hat{a} .
- (2) Apply a correct transformation \mathcal{T} with the assumptions H and the abstraction \hat{a} to generate a high-level program.

Figure 5 summarizes a single stage of the binary lifting process. The static analysis \mathcal{A} analyzes the program p_L and then the syntactic transformation \mathcal{T} transforms p_L using the assumptions H and the abstraction \hat{a} to the high-level program p_H . The trace τ_L is filtered to the trace τ_H for assumptions H using the filtering relation \supseteq . For any trace-assumption-trace triple (τ_L, H, τ_H) , τ_L is related to τ_H using the relation \sim . By using the same assumptions as the transformation, we can show that the high-level trace τ_H is related to the low-level trace τ_L using the relation \sim .

4.3 Correctness Proof

We prove that Proposition 4.6 holds for each lifting stage in four steps. The first two prove the properties of the filtering relation \supseteq and the last two prove the properties of the transformation \mathcal{T} .

PROPOSITION 4.7 (FILTERING PRESERVES SIMULATION). *For a filtering relation \supseteq , H , p_L , τ_L , and τ_H , $(H, p_L \vdash \tau_L \supseteq \tau_H) \Rightarrow (\tau_L \sim \tau_H)$*

PROPOSITION 4.8 (UNIQUENESS OF FILTERING). *For a filtering relation \supseteq , H , p_L , τ_L , τ_H , and τ'_H , $(H, p_L \vdash \tau_L \supseteq \tau_H) \wedge (H, p_L \vdash \tau_L \supseteq \tau'_H) \Rightarrow \tau_H = \tau'_H$*

PROPOSITION 4.9 (SIMULATION FROM HIGH-LEVEL TO LOW-LEVEL). *For a transformation \mathcal{T} , a filtering relation \supseteq , assumptions H , a program p_L , τ_L , τ_H , \hat{a} , and σ_H , if \hat{a} is sound for \supseteq , H , and p_L , $(H, p_L \vdash \tau_L \supseteq \tau_H) \wedge (\mathcal{T}(p_L, H, \hat{a}) \vdash \tau_H \cdot \sigma_H) \Rightarrow \exists \sigma_L, (H, p_L \vdash \tau_L \cdot \sigma_L \supseteq \tau_H \cdot \sigma_H)$*

PROPOSITION 4.10 (CORRESPONDENCE OF FILTERING AND TRANSFORMATION). *For a transformation \mathcal{T} , a filtering relation \supseteq , assumptions H , a program p_L , τ_L , τ_H , and \hat{a} , if \hat{a} is sound for \supseteq , H , and p_L ,*

$$\begin{aligned} (H, p_L \vdash \tau_L \supseteq \tau_H) &\Rightarrow (\mathcal{T}(p_L, H, \hat{a}) \vdash \tau_H) \\ (p_L \vdash \tau_L) \wedge (\mathcal{T}(p_L, H, \hat{a}) \vdash \tau_H) \wedge (\tau_L \sim \tau_H) &\Rightarrow (H, p_L \vdash \tau_L \supseteq \tau_H) \end{aligned}$$

p_{IL} : ILIR Program $p_{IL} ::= [(w \mapsto i_{IL}), \bar{w}]$ i_{IL} : Instruction $i_{IL} ::=$ assign $r e$ load $r b$ store $b b$ jmp b cjmp $b w$ nop	e : Expression $e ::=$ b $b \oplus b$ $\oplus b$ r : Register b : Basic Expression $b ::= r \mid w$ w : Word = \mathbb{B}^{64}	σ : ILIR State $\sigma ::= (w, \Gamma, M)$ M : Memory \mathcal{M} $M ::= w \mapsto w$ Γ : Register File $\Gamma ::= r \mapsto w$ (b) State
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(a) Syntax

Fig. 6. Syntax and state of ILIR

With these propositions, we prove the correctness of the transformation for each lifting stage.

THEOREM 4.11. *If \hat{a} is sound for a filtering relation \triangleright and assumptions H that satisfy Propositions 4.7 to 4.10, then Proposition 4.6 holds for p_L and $\mathcal{T}(p_L, H, \hat{a})$.*

PROOF. The first property of Definition 4.3 is satisfied by Propositions 4.7, 4.9 and 4.10. To prove the second property, suppose there exists τ'_H such that for $\tau_L, \sigma_L, \tau'_H$, and $\sigma_H, H, p_L \vdash \tau_L \cdot \sigma_L \triangleright \tau'_H \cdot \sigma_H$. Because the filtering relation holds for prefixes of a trace, we can derive $H, p_L \vdash \tau_L \triangleright \tau'_H$. By Proposition 4.8, we can derive $\tau_H = \tau'_H$. \square

We have developed a formal framework for static analysis and program transformation with assumptions. In subsequent sections, we define the static analysis and transformation for each lifting stage and provide a proof sketch of Propositions 4.7 to 4.10.

5 CFG Reconstruction

This section describes how we define the first stage of our binary lifting process, CFG reconstruction. We define the low-level language L_{IL} (5.1), the high-level language L_{FG} (5.2), the simulation relation \sim and the filtering relation \triangleright (5.3), the static analysis \mathcal{A} (5.4), and the transformation \mathcal{T} (5.5).

5.1 Instruction-Level IR (ILIR)

The first language we define is the instruction-level IR (ILIR), which is designed to uniformly describe the semantics of a single instruction across various architectures. Its goal is to precisely represent machine instructions while omitting architecture-specific details. We have examined existing executable instruction-level IRs, such as QEMU TCG [9], ESIL [47], and the first-stage IR of IDA-Pro and Ghidra, and define the ILIR as shown in Figure 6. It is widely-used as a standard model for machines and used in an educational compiler [4].

We define the syntax of ILIR in Figure 6a. The program is a map from addresses to instructions, with possible entry points as a list of addresses. The instructions include assignment (**assign** $r e$), load (**load** $r b$), store (**store** $b b$), jump (**jmp** b), conditional jump (**cjmp** $b w$), and no operation (**nop**). The assignment instruction simply assigns a value of evaluating e to a variable. The load instruction transfers a value from memory to a variable, while the store instruction moves a value from a variable to memory. The jump instruction directs control to an address specified by a basic expression, and the conditional jump instruction does so if the value of the expression is non-zero. A basic expression can either be a constant word w or a register r .

We do not distinguish between call and return instructions in the instruction-level IR. Although the assembly program which is the source of the ILIR program may have instructions named

$$\boxed{p_{IL} \vdash \sigma \rightsquigarrow \sigma'}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{[ILIR-assign]} \frac{p_{IL}(w_{pc}) = \mathbf{assign} \ r \ e \quad \Gamma \vdash e \Downarrow w}{p_{IL} \vdash (w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \rightsquigarrow (w_{pc} + 1, \Gamma[r \mapsto w], M)} \\
\text{[ILIR-load]} \frac{p_{IL}(w_{pc}) = \mathbf{load} \ r \ b \quad \Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w \quad M(w) = w'}{p_{IL} \vdash (w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \rightsquigarrow (w_{pc} + 1, \Gamma[r \mapsto w'], M)} \\
\text{[ILIR-store]} \frac{p_{IL}(w_{pc}) = \mathbf{store} \ b_1 \ b_2 \quad \Gamma \vdash b_1 \Downarrow w_1 \quad \Gamma \vdash b_2 \Downarrow w_2}{p_{IL} \vdash (w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \rightsquigarrow (w_{pc} + 1, \Gamma, M[w_1 \mapsto w_2])} \\
\text{[ILIR-jmp]} \frac{p_{IL}(w_{pc}) = \mathbf{jmp} \ b \quad \Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w}{p_{IL} \vdash (w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \rightsquigarrow (w, \Gamma, M)} \\
\text{[ILIR-cjmp-true]} \frac{p_{IL}(w_{pc}) = \mathbf{cjmp} \ b_1 \ w_1 \quad \Gamma \vdash b_1 \Downarrow w \quad w \neq 0}{p_{IL} \vdash (w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \rightsquigarrow (w_1, \Gamma, M)} \\
\text{[ILIR-cjmp-false]} \frac{p_{IL}(w_{pc}) = \mathbf{cjmp} \ b_1 \ w_1 \quad \Gamma \vdash b_1 \Downarrow w \quad w = 0}{p_{IL} \vdash (w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \rightsquigarrow (w_{pc} + 1, \Gamma, M)} \\
\text{[ILIR-nop]} \frac{p_{IL}(w_{pc}) = \mathbf{nop}}{p_{IL} \vdash (w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \rightsquigarrow (w_{pc} + 1, \Gamma, M)}
\end{array}$$

Fig. 7. Small-step semantics of ILIR

call and ret, we treat them as only hints for the analysis, not as a part of the source program. It is because call and ret in the assembly are only syntactic sugar for saving and restoring the return address to designated stack memory/register and jumping to the target address. It does not guarantee that the jump is a function call or return. For example, the call instruction in the assembly program may be used as an intra-procedural jump pushing the return address from the stack to access the current program counter.

We define a state of the ILIR in Figure 6b. A state σ consists of a memory M , a register file Γ , and a program counter w . A Memory M is a map from addresses to values, and a register file Γ is a map from registers to values. A program counter w is an address pointing to the current instruction.

We define the small-step semantics of the instruction-level IR in Figure 7. For non-jump instructions such as assignment, load, and store, it updates the register or memory and increments the program counter. For a jump instruction, it updates the program counter to the value of the expression. For a conditional jump instruction, it updates the program counter to the target address if the value of the first expression is non-zero; otherwise, it just increases the program counter. We omit the semantics of binary and unary operations, as they are not essential for describing the subsequent lifting process. We just use notation $\Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w$ or $\Gamma \vdash e \Downarrow w$ to denote the evaluation of an expression b or e to a value w for a given register file Γ and memory M .

5.2 Flow-Graph IR (FGIR)

The Flow-Graph IR (FGIR) is a graph-based model in which each node represents a jump instruction, and each edge indicates the control flow between these instructions. To define the syntax of FGIR,

$p_{FG} : \overline{\text{FGIR Program}}$	$j_{FG} : \text{Jump}$	
$p_{FG} ::= \overline{f_{FG}}$	$j_{FG} ::= \mathbf{call? } b \ w$	
$f_{FG} : \text{Function}$	$\mid \mathbf{tailcall? } b$	$\sigma : \text{FGIR State}$
$f_{FG} ::= \mathbf{func } w \ (\overline{w, j_{FG}})$	$\mid \mathbf{ret? } b$	$\sigma ::= (\delta, w_f, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M)$
$i_{FG} ::= \mathbf{assign } r \ e$	$\mid \mathbf{fallthrough } i_{FG} \ w$	$\delta : \text{Call Stack}$
$\mid \mathbf{load } r \ b$	$\mid \mathbf{branch } b \ w \ w$	$\delta ::= (\overline{w_f, w_{ret}})$
$\mid \mathbf{store } b \ b$	$\mid \mathbf{goto } w$	(b) State
$\mid \mathbf{nop}$	$\mid \mathbf{goto_ind } b \ \overline{w}$	

(a) Syntax

Fig. 8. Syntax and state of FGIR

$$\boxed{\Gamma, M \vdash i_{FG} \Rightarrow \Gamma', M'}$$

$$[\text{FGIR-assign}] \frac{\Gamma \vdash e \Downarrow w}{\Gamma, M \vdash \mathbf{assign } r \ e \Rightarrow \Gamma[r \mapsto w], M} \quad [\text{FGIR-load}] \frac{\Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w \quad M(w) = w'}{\Gamma, M \vdash \mathbf{load } r \ b \Rightarrow \Gamma[r \mapsto w'], M}$$

$$[\text{FGIR-store}] \frac{\Gamma \vdash b_1 \Downarrow w_1 \quad \Gamma \vdash b_2 \Downarrow w_2}{\Gamma, M \vdash \mathbf{store } b_1 \ b_2 \Rightarrow \Gamma, M[w_1 \mapsto w_2]} \quad [\text{FGIR-nop}] \frac{}{\Gamma, M \vdash \mathbf{nop} \Rightarrow \Gamma, M}$$

Fig. 9. Small-step semantics of FGIR

we analyze real-world IRs, such as BIL's Cfg. AST module [13] and B2R2's SSA module [29] capturing their core concepts.

We define the syntax of FGIR in Figure 8a. The syntax of FGIR is different from ILIR in many aspects. First, a FGIR program is now a list of functions, different from the ILIR program which consists of instruction memory and a list of entry points. Second, a jump is categorized to distinguish intra-procedural jumps and function calls: **call?**, **tailcall?**, **ret?**, **fallthrough**, **branch**, **goto**, and **goto_ind**. Third, all intra-procedural jumps are bounded, which means that all possible targets of a jump instruction are shown in the instruction itself. We define a helper function $\text{succ}(j_{FG})$ to get possible target addresses of a jump instruction j_{FG} .

A program state of FGIR is defined in Figure 8b. A state σ is defined as a 5-tuple $(\delta, w_f, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M)$, where δ is the call stack, with each item in the call stack consisting of a pair of a function address and a return address; w_f is the address of the current function; w_{pc} is the program counter; Γ is the register file; and M is the memory. The difference between the FGIR state and the ILIR state is that the FGIR state additionally includes the call stack and the current function address.

We define the small-step semantics of FGIR in Figure 9. We use the helper function $\text{func}(p_{FG}, w_f) = \mathbf{func } w_f \ \text{cfg}$ to find the function with the entry address w_f in the program p_{FG} .

- [FGIR-call] rule describes that the semantics of a call instruction **call?** $b \ w_{ret}$ in a function w_f at w_{pc} is to push the current function address and the return address (w_f, w_{ret}) on top of the call stack and change the program counter to the call target w .
- [FGIR-tailcall] rule describes that the semantics of a tail call instruction **tailcall?** b is to change the program counter to the call target w without pushing the current function address and the return address on the call stack.

$$\boxed{p_{FG} \vdash \sigma \rightsquigarrow \sigma'}$$

[FGIR-call]

$$\frac{\text{func}(p_{FG}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ w_f \ \text{cfg} \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{call?} \ b \ w_{ret}) \in \text{cfg} \quad \Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w}{p_{FG} \vdash (\delta, w_f, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \rightsquigarrow ((w_f, w_{ret}) :: \delta, w, w, \Gamma, M)}$$

[FGIR-tailcall]

$$\frac{\text{func}(p_{FG}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ w_f \ \text{cfg} \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{tailcall?} \ b) \in \text{cfg} \quad \Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w}{p_{FG} \vdash (\delta, w_f, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \rightsquigarrow (\delta, w, w, \Gamma, M)}$$

[FGIR-ret]

$$\frac{\text{func}(p_{FG}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ w_f \ \text{cfg} \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{ret?} \ b) \in \text{cfg} \quad \Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w_{ret}}{p_{FG} \vdash ((w_f', w_{ret}) :: \delta, w_f, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \rightsquigarrow (\delta, w_f', w_{ret}, \Gamma, M)}$$

[FGIR-fallthrough]

$$\frac{\text{func}(p_{FG}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ w_f \ \text{cfg} \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{fallthrough} \ i_{FG} \ w) \in \text{cfg} \quad \Gamma, M \vdash i_{FG} \Rightarrow \Gamma', M'}{p_{FG} \vdash (\delta, w_f, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \rightsquigarrow (\delta, w_f, w, \Gamma', M')}$$

[FGIR-branch-true]

$$\frac{\text{func}(p_{FG}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ w_f \ \text{cfg} \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{branch} \ b \ w_1 \ w_2) \in \text{cfg} \quad \Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w \quad w \neq 0}{p_{FG} \vdash (\delta, w_f, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \rightsquigarrow (\delta, w_f, w_1, \Gamma, M)}$$

[FGIR-branch-false]

$$\frac{\text{func}(p_{FG}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ w_f \ \text{cfg} \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{branch} \ b \ w_1 \ w_2) \in \text{cfg} \quad \Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w \quad w = 0}{p_{FG} \vdash (\delta, w_f, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \rightsquigarrow (\delta, w_f, w_2, \Gamma, M)}$$

[FGIR-goto]

$$\frac{\text{func}(p_{FG}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ w_f \ \text{cfg} \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{goto} \ w) \in \text{cfg}}{p_{FG} \vdash (\delta, w_f, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \rightsquigarrow (\delta, w_f, w, \Gamma, M)}$$

[FGIR-gotoind]

$$\frac{\text{func}(p_{FG}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ w_f \ \text{cfg} \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{goto_ind} \ b \ \bar{w}) \in \text{cfg} \quad \Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w' \quad w' \in \bar{w}}{p_{FG} \vdash (\delta, w_f, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \rightsquigarrow (\delta, w_f, w', \Gamma, M)}$$

Fig. 9 (cont.). Small-step semantics of FGIR

- [FGIR-ret] rule describes that the semantics of a return instruction **ret?** b is to check whether the return target w_{ret} is the same as the return address on the top of the call stack, pop the topmost call stack frame (w_f, w_{ret}) , and change the function address to the return function address w_f and the program counter to the return address w_{ret} .
- [FGIR-fallthrough] rule describes that the semantics of a fallthrough instruction **fallthrough** $i_{FG} \ w$ is to execute the instruction i_{FG} and change the program counter to the fallthrough address w .
- [FGIR-branch-true] and [FGIR-branch-false] rules describe that the semantics of a branch instruction **branch** $b \ w_1 \ w_2$ is to check whether the condition b is true or false and change the program counter to the corresponding target address w_1 or w_2 .
- [FGIR-goto] rule describes that the semantics of a goto instruction **goto** w is to change the program counter to the jump target w .

- [FGIR-gotoind] rule describes that the semantics of an indirect call instruction **goto_ind** $b \bar{w}$ is to check whether the jump target w' is in the list of possible target addresses \bar{w} and change the program counter to the jump target.

Jump instructions ending with ? may fail to step to the next state due to the following reasons:

- **call?** and **tailcall?** may fail if their target functions are not found in the current program.
- **ret?** may fail if the return address is not found in the current program or the return address is different from the expected return address in the call stack.

5.3 Simulation Relation and Filtering Relation from ILIR to FGIR

To reconstruct CFGs from ILIR, we should reconstruct intra-procedural control flows from ILIR, which are paths of control flows within individual functions. Since not every trace in ILIR is a valid trace in FGIR, we define a filtering relation between ILIR traces and FGIR traces to identify intra-procedural control flows in FGIR.

Unfortunately, ILIR programs do not have explicit information about function boundaries, so we need to identify function boundaries and discover intra-procedural control flows at the same time, which requires determining whether a jump instruction is a call, a return, or an intra-procedural jump. These determinations are not always possible, so we introduce assumptions about jump instructions and use them to reconstruct control flows. We use four kinds of assumptions: (W_T, W_C, W_R, W_J) where W_T is the set of tail call addresses, W_C is the set of call addresses, W_R is the set of return addresses, and W_J is the set of jump addresses. We require that the assumptions are disjoint, i.e. for any pairs of sets $A, B \in \{W_T, W_C, W_R, W_J\}$, $A \cap B = \emptyset$.

We define the simulation relation \sim between ILIR states and FGIR states as follows:

Definition 5.1 (Simulation relation between ILIR and FGIR states). Given an ILIR state (w_{pc}, Γ, M) and an FGIR state $(\delta, w_f, w'_{pc}, \Gamma', M')$, the simulation relation is defined as follows:

$$(w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \sim (\delta, w_f, w'_{pc}, \Gamma', M') \iff w_{pc} = w'_{pc} \wedge \Gamma = \Gamma' \wedge M = M'$$

We define the filtering relation as a relation $(W_T, W_C, W_R, W_J), p_{IL} \vdash \tau_{IL} \supseteq \tau'_{FG}$, where τ_{IL} is an ILIR trace, τ'_{FG} is an FGIR trace, and (W_T, W_C, W_R, W_J) are assumptions. The filtering relation is inductively defined as shown in Figure 10:

- [TCF-single] rule is the base case of the filtering relation. It states that 1) a single ILIR state with a program counter that is a function entry point is valid and 2) an extension of the ILIR state with the empty call stack and the current program counter as a function address is a related FGIR state.
- [TCF-jump] rule describes the filtering relation of a jump instruction. It simply updates the program counter to the jump target.
- [TCF-call] rule describes the filtering relation of a call instruction. It pushes a pair of the current function address w_f and the next address of the current program counter $w_{pc} + 1$ as a return address on top of the call stack and changes the program counter to the call target w'_{pc} .
- [TCF-tailcall] rule describes the filtering relation of a tail call instruction. It does not change the call stack, and changes the program counter and the current function to the tail call target.
- [TCF-return] rule describes the filtering relation of a return instruction. It checks whether the return target w_{ret} is the same as the return address on the top of the call stack, pops the topmost call stack frame (w_f, w_{ret}) , and changes the program counter to the return target.

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{[TCF-single]} \frac{p_{IL} \vdash \langle (w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \rangle \quad (w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \in f^{\text{init}}(p_{IL})}{(W_T, W_C, W_R, W_J), p_{IL} \vdash \langle (w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \rangle \supseteq \langle ([], w_{pc}, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \rangle} \\
\text{[TCF-jump]} \frac{(W_T, W_C, W_R, W_J), p_{IL} \vdash \tau_{IL} \supseteq \tau'_{FG} \quad \tau'_{FG} = \tau''_{FG} \cdot (\delta, w_f, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \quad w_{pc} \in W_J \quad p_{IL} \vdash \tau_{IL} \cdot (w'_{pc}, \Gamma', M')}{(W_T, W_C, W_R, W_J), p_{IL} \vdash \tau_{IL} \cdot (w'_{pc}, \Gamma', M') \supseteq \tau'_{FG} \cdot (\delta, w_f, w'_{pc}, \Gamma', M')} \\
\text{[TCF-call]} \frac{(W_T, W_C, W_R, W_J), p_{IL} \vdash \tau_{IL} \supseteq \tau'_{FG} \quad \tau'_{FG} = \tau''_{FG} \cdot (\delta, w_f, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \quad w_{pc} \in W_C \quad p_{IL} \vdash \tau_{IL} \cdot (w'_{pc}, \Gamma', M')}{(W_T, W_C, W_R, W_J), p_{IL} \vdash \tau_{IL} \cdot (w'_{pc}, \Gamma', M') \supseteq \tau'_{FG} \cdot ((w_f, w_{pc} + 1) :: \delta, w'_{pc}, w'_{pc}, \Gamma', M')} \\
\text{[TCF-tailcall]} \frac{(W_T, W_C, W_R, W_J), p_{IL} \vdash \tau_{IL} \supseteq \tau'_{FG} \quad \tau'_{FG} = \tau''_{FG} \cdot (\delta, w_f, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \quad w_{pc} \in W_T \quad p_{IL} \vdash \tau_{IL} \cdot (w'_{pc}, \Gamma', M')}{(W_T, W_C, W_R, W_J), p_{IL} \vdash \tau_{IL} \cdot (w'_{pc}, \Gamma', M') \supseteq \tau'_{FG} \cdot (\delta, w'_{pc}, w'_{pc}, \Gamma', M')} \\
\text{[TCF-return]} \frac{(W_T, W_C, W_R, W_J), p_{IL} \vdash \tau_{IL} \supseteq \tau'_{FG} \quad \tau'_{FG} = \tau''_{FG} \cdot ((w_f, w_{ret}) :: \delta, w_f, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \quad w_{pc} \in W_R \quad p_{IL} \vdash \tau_{IL} \cdot (w_{ret}, \Gamma', M')}{(W_T, W_C, W_R, W_J), p_{IL} \vdash \tau_{IL} \cdot (w_{ret}, \Gamma', M') \supseteq \tau'_{FG} \cdot (\delta, w_f, w_{ret}, \Gamma', M')}
\end{array}$$

Fig. 10. Filtering relation from an ILIR trace to an FGIR trace

Because FGIR is designed to represent the filtering of the ILIR program in a language, the semantics of FGIR itself are almost the same as the filtering relation. For example, the rule [FGIR-call] corresponds to the filtering rule [TCF-call], and the rule [FGIR-ret] corresponds to the filtering rule [TCF-ret]. The only rule that requires more than filtering is the rule [FGIR-gotoind], which requires the target address to be in the list of possible target addresses.

Proof sketch of proposition 4.7. For [TCF-single], the base case, the simulation relation is trivial. For all other rules, they just update the call stack and current function and do not change the program counter, register file and memory, so the simulation relation is satisfied. Also because all rules require the validity of the trace, the validity of the trace is preserved.

Proof sketch of proposition 4.8. Because the assumption is disjoint, there is only one rule that can be applied to the trace determined by the last state of the trace. Therefore, the filtering relation is unique.

5.4 Control Flow Analysis

Static analysis to reconstruct intra-procedural control flows is called *control flow analysis*. Kinder et al. [30] formalize a control flow analysis for JUMP language, which is similar to ILIR, without call/return instructions. We use their formulation as a basis for control flow analysis and extend it to support call/return instructions.

We formalize control flow analysis of a single function entry using constraint-style inference rules in Figure 11. The control flow analysis is a static analysis that takes a program p_{IL} and a single function entry address w_e and returns $(W_T, W_C, W_R, W_J), \hat{a}$, where $W_T, W_C, W_R,$ and W_J are the sets of tail call, call, return, and jump instructions, respectively, and \hat{a} is the abstract state. We do not explicitly define the abstract state, as it is not essential to fix a single analysis domain. Instead, we assume that we can use the abstract state with three helper functions: $succ^\#$, $post^\#$, and $\Gamma^\#$. The $succ^\#$ function returns the set of successors of a given address, and the $post^\#$ function takes the

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{[SCF-jump]} \frac{h(p_{IL}, w) = J}{w \in W_J \quad \perp \sqsubset \hat{a}_w \wedge w_{next} \in succ^\#(\hat{a}_w) \Rightarrow post^\#(\hat{a}_w, w_{next}) \sqsubseteq \hat{a}_{w_{next}}} \\
\text{[SCF-entry]} \frac{w_e \in f^{init}(p_{IL})}{\top \sqsubseteq \hat{a}_{w_e}} \quad \text{[SCF-call]} \frac{h(p_{IL}, w) = C}{w \in W_C \quad \perp \sqsubset \hat{a}_w \Rightarrow \top \sqsubseteq \hat{a}_{w+1}} \\
\text{[SCF-tailcall]} \frac{h(p_{IL}, w) = T}{w \in W_T \quad \perp \sqsubset \hat{a}_w \Rightarrow \top \sqsubseteq \hat{a}_{w+1}} \quad \text{[SCF-ret]} \frac{h(p_{IL}, w) = R}{w \in W_R}
\end{array}$$

Fig. 11. Control flow analysis

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}((W_T, W_C, W_R, W_J), p_{IL}, \bar{\bar{a}}) &= \bigcup_{w_e \in f^{init}(p_{IL})} \mathcal{T}_f((W_T, W_C, W_R, W_J), w_e, p_{IL}, \bar{\bar{a}}_{w_e}) \\
\mathcal{T}_f((W_T, W_C, W_R, W_J), w_e, p_{IL}, \bar{\bar{a}}) &= \bigcup_{\hat{a}_{w_{pc}} \in \bar{\bar{a}}} \mathcal{T}_i((W_T, W_C, W_R, W_J), w_{pc}, p_{IL}, abs_reg(\hat{a}_{w_{pc}})) \\
\mathcal{T}_i((W_T, W_C, W_R, W_J), w_{pc}, p_{IL}, \Gamma^\#) &= \left\{ \begin{array}{ll}
\text{call? } b \ w_{pc} + 1 & \text{if } p_{IL}(w_{pc}) = \mathbf{jmp} \ b \wedge w_{pc} \in W_C \\
\text{tailcall? } b & \text{if } p_{IL}(w_{pc}) = \mathbf{jmp} \ b \wedge w_{pc} \in W_T \\
\text{ret? } b & \text{if } p_{IL}(w_{pc}) = \mathbf{jmp} \ b \wedge w_{pc} \in W_R \\
\text{fallthrough } p_{IL}(w_{pc}) \ w_{pc} + 1 & \text{if } p_{IL}(w_{pc}) = \mathbf{assign} \ r \ e \mid \mathbf{load} \ r \ b \\
& \quad \mid \mathbf{store} \ b_1 \ b_2 \mid \mathbf{nop} \\
\text{branch } b \ w \ w_{pc} + 1 & \text{if } p_{IL}(w_{pc}) = \mathbf{cjmp} \ b \ w \\
\text{goto } w & \text{if } p_{IL}(w_{pc}) = \mathbf{jmp} \ w \wedge w_{pc} \in W_J \\
\text{goto_ind } r \ \bar{w} & \text{if } p_{IL}(w_{pc}) = \mathbf{jmp} \ r \wedge w_{pc} \in W_J \\
& \quad \wedge \Gamma^\#(r) = \bar{w}
\end{array} \right.
\end{aligned}$$

Fig. 12. FGIR transformation

abstract state and an address and returns the abstract state which reaches the address after one step. During the analysis, we use the heuristic function h to determine the type of instruction at a given address. $h(p_{IL}, w)$ returns the type of instruction at address w . The $\Gamma^\#$ function returns the abstract register file, which is used to determine the target of an indirect jump.

The analysis result of a whole program is the union of the analysis results of all functions in the program.

5.5 FGIR transformation

Finally, we define the transformation from ILIR to FGIR. The transformation consists of three parts: the instruction-level transformation \mathcal{T}_i , the function-level transformation \mathcal{T}_f , and the whole program transformation \mathcal{T} . The instruction-level transformation maps each ILIR instruction to its corresponding FGIR jump using assumptions and the abstract state as shown in Figure 12. We denote a helper function abs_reg that extracts the abstract register file from the abstract state. The function-level transformation and the whole program transformation are simply compositions of the instruction-level transformation.

p_{AS}	:	ASIR Program	j_{AS}	::=	call? b n_{diff} n_{copy} w
p_{AS}	::=	prog r f_{AS}			tailcall? b n_{diff} n_{copy}
f_{AS}	::=	func n_{diff} n_{min} n_{max} \bar{n} w $\overline{(w, j_{AS})}$			ret
i_{AS}	::=	assign r e			fallthrough i_{AS} w
		load? r b			branch? b w w
		store? b b			goto w
		lload r n			goto_ind? b \bar{w}
		lstore b n			
		nop			

(a) Syntax

v	:	ASIR Value	Γ	::=	$r \mapsto v$
v	::=	w	M	::=	$w \mapsto v$
		undef	μ	:	Local memory
		sp w_f t n	μ	::=	$cf \mapsto (n_{min}, n_{max}, (n \mapsto v))$
t	:	Tick	cf	:	Current function
t	\in	$\mathbb{T} = \mathbb{N}$	cf	::=	$\overline{(w_f, t_f)}$
σ	::=	$(\delta, cf, t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu)$	δ	::=	$\overline{(cf, w_{ret}, v)}$

(b) State

Fig. 13. Syntax and state of ASIR

Proof sketch of proposition 4.9. Suppose an FGIR trace is extended by a single step. Because the small-step semantics of FGIR and the filtering relation of ILIR are structurally similar, we can apply corresponding filtering rules to the ILIR trace. All rules of the small-step semantics of FGIR except [FGIR-gotoind] have the same premises as their corresponding filtering rules of ILIR. For [FGIR-gotoind], we can use the definition of the transformation $\Gamma^\sharp(r) = \bar{w}$ and the property of a sound analysis to ensure that the ILIR trace is filtered correctly. Therefore, the ILIR trace is also extended by a single filtering rule if the FGIR trace is extended by a single step.

We omit the proof sketch of Proposition 4.10 because the reasoning is similar to the proof of Proposition 4.9 by case analysis of the ILIR filtering relation.

6 Abstract Stack Reconstruction

The second stage of our binary lifting process reconstructs abstract stack and local memory.

6.1 Abstract-Stack IR (ASIR)

After reconstructing function boundaries and the call stack in the first stage, the next step is to separate global and local memory. Global memory is shared among all functions, and local memory is usually used for the current function unless a pointer to local memory is passed to another function. Reconstruction of the abstract stack from the physical stack enables complex analysis more scalable [5, 6]. Most lifters of LLVM IR or decompiler IRs perform this step using common modeling of stack frames, which is access patterns of stack-related addresses.

The syntax of ASIR is shown in Figure 13a. The major difference between ASIR and FGIR programs is that it has annotations for the stack layout for function definition and call instructions. Also, the call instructions are annotated with the difference in the stack pointer, the number of stack spaces to copy, and the return address. There is also a difference in memory access instructions. There are

two kinds of memory access instructions: **lload/lstore** for only local memory and **load/store** for generic memory access.

The definition of the value and the state of ASIR is shown in Figure 13b. The value is a word, a special value **undef** describing the undefined value, or a stack pointer value. The stack pointer value is a tuple of the function address, the tick, and the offset. The tick is a natural number that represents the number of function calls, to distinguish the same function call multiple times. The offset is a natural number that represents the offset from the stack pointer.

We define the ASIR state as a 7-tuple $(\delta, cf, t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu)$ where δ is the call stack, cf is the current function, t is the tick, w_{pc} is the program counter, Γ is the register file, M is the memory, and μ is the local memory. The local memory is a map from the function address and the tick to the minimum and maximum offsets and the memory. The call stack is a list of the tuple of the function address, the return address, and the stack pointer value.

The semantics of ASIR is shown in Figure 14. We denote $p_{AS}, cf, \Gamma, M, \mu \vdash i \Rightarrow \Gamma', M', \mu'$ as the execution of an instruction i in the program p_{AS} with the current function cf , the register file Γ , the global memory M , and the local memory μ . We denote $p_{AS} \vdash \sigma \rightsquigarrow \sigma'$ as the transition of the state σ to the state σ' .

We use the helper functions *local_mem_split* and *local_mem_merge* to split and merge the local memory, respectively. *local_mem_split* $(\mu, (w_f, t), (w_{f'}, t'), n, n_{copy})$ creates new local memory by copying the local memory space referenced by (w_f, t) , with the range of offset $[n - n_{copy}, n]$, to $(w_{f'}, t')$ with the range of offset $[-n_{copy}, 0]$. *local_mem_merge* $(\mu, (w_f, t), (w_{f'}, t'), n)$ creates new local memory by copying all local memory space referenced by $(w_{f'}, t')$ to (w_f, t) with difference of offset n .

The core difference in the semantics is that the memory access instructions are annotated with the memory region to access. The **lload/lstore** instructions are only allowed to access local memory, and the **load?/store?** instructions are allowed to generic memory access. We cannot restrict generic memory access to only global memory, because the stack pointer is often passed as an argument to the function, and it is used as same as the global memory pointer. However, the rule ASIR-STORE-2 enforces that specific local memory regions are only accessible by the local memory access instructions, to make arbitrary memory access to change the stored return address or stack pointer an undefined behavior.

6.2 Simulation Relation and Filtering Relation from FGIR to ASIR

To reconstruct the abstract stack layout, we need to define necessary constraints to filter out FGIR traces that do not correspond to ASIR traces. However, unlike CFG reconstruction, identifying these constraints is not straightforward at this stage, so we manually examined the analysis in the lifters and observed the following:

- For each call instruction, the analyzers assume that the stack pointer changes by a fixed amount. For most calling conventions, this value is zero, but for some calling conventions that require callees to clean up the stack, such as GNU fast call for x86 [26], the amount of change in the stack pointer is a non-zero value.
- Analyzers assume that the saved return address does not change during a function call.

Based on these observations, we make two assumptions: the stack pointer register r_{sp} and the function signature f_{sig} , which is $(n_{diff}, n_{min}, n_{max}, N, W, f_{call})$.

n_{diff} is the difference of stack pointer for return instructions, n_{min} and n_{max} denote the minimum and maximum offsets of the local memory accesses, respectively. N and W are about safe stack access. Because the lifter generally does not track every stack access precisely, they assume that the only store in the stack at the index in N happens at the address in W . It prevents imprecise

$$\boxed{p_{AS}, cf, \Gamma, M, \mu \vdash i_{AS} \Rightarrow \Gamma', M', \mu'}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{[ASIR-assign]} \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash e \Downarrow v}{p_{AS}, cf, \Gamma, M, \mu \vdash \mathbf{assign} \ r \ e \Rightarrow \Gamma[r \mapsto v], M, \mu} \\
\text{[ASIR-load-1]} \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w \quad M(w) = v}{p_{AS}, cf, \Gamma, M, \mu \vdash \mathbf{load?} \ r \ b \Rightarrow \Gamma[r \mapsto v], M, \mu} \\
\text{[ASIR-load-2]} \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow \mathbf{sp} \ w_f \ t \ n' \quad \mathit{func}(p_{AS}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ n_{diff} \ n_{min} \ n_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w_f \ (\overline{w}, j) \quad n_{min} \leq n' \leq n_{max} \quad \mu((w_f, t), n') = v}{p_{AS}, cf, \Gamma, M, \mu \vdash \mathbf{load?} \ r \ b \Rightarrow \Gamma[r \mapsto v], M, \mu} \\
\text{[ASIR-load-3]} \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow \mathbf{undef}}{p_{AS}, cf, \Gamma, M, \mu \vdash \mathbf{load?} \ r \ b \Rightarrow \Gamma[r \mapsto \mathbf{undef}], M, \mu} \\
\text{[ASIR-store-1]} \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash b_1 \Downarrow w \quad \Gamma \vdash b_2 \Downarrow v}{p_{AS}, cf, \Gamma, M, \mu \vdash \mathbf{store?} \ b_1 \ b_2 \Rightarrow \Gamma, M[w \mapsto v], \mu} \\
\text{[ASIR-store-2]} \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash b_1 \Downarrow \mathbf{sp} \ w_f \ t \ n' \quad \mathit{func}(p_{AS}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ n_{diff} \ n_{min} \ n_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w_f \ (\overline{w}, j) \quad n_{min} \leq n' \leq n_{max} \quad n' \notin \bar{n} \quad \Gamma \vdash b_2 \Downarrow v}{p_{AS}, cf, \Gamma, M, \mu \vdash \mathbf{store?} \ b_1 \ b_2 \Rightarrow \Gamma, M, \mu[(w_f, t), n'] \mapsto v} \\
\text{[ASIR-lload]} \\
\frac{\mu(cf, n) = v}{p_{AS}, cf, \Gamma, M, \mu \vdash \mathbf{lload} \ r \ n \Rightarrow \Gamma[r \mapsto v], M, \mu} \\
\text{[ASIR-lstore]} \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow v}{p_{AS}, cf, \Gamma, M, \mu \vdash \mathbf{lstore} \ b \ n \Rightarrow \Gamma, M, \mu[(cf, n) \mapsto v]} \\
\text{[ASIR-nop]} \\
\frac{}{p_{AS}, cf, \Gamma, M, \mu \vdash \mathbf{nop} \Rightarrow \Gamma, M, \mu}
\end{array}$$

Fig. 14. Small step semantics of ASIR

stores from polluting the stack to overwrite the return address and saved stack pointer. The f_{call} is the information about the call instruction, which element is a tuple (n_{diff}, n_{copy}) where n_{diff} is the difference of stack pointer before and after the call instruction, and n_{copy} is the size of bytes to copy from the caller local memory to the callee local memory.

To represent the simulation relation between FGIR and ASIR states, we define the simulation relation between two memories. Because the value of the target language is more abstract, we

$$\boxed{p_{AS} \vdash \sigma \rightsquigarrow \sigma'}$$

[ASIR-call]

$$\frac{p_{AS} = \mathbf{prog} \ r_{sp} \ \bar{f} \quad \mathit{func}(p_{AS}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ n_{diff} \ n_{min} \ n_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w_f \ \mathit{cfg} \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{call?} \ b \ n'_{diff} \ n_{copy} \ w_{ret}) \in \mathit{cfg} \quad \Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w_{f'}}{\mathit{func}(p_{AS}, w_{f'}) = \mathbf{func} \ n'_{diff} \ n'_{min} \ n'_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w_{f'} \ \mathit{cfg} \quad \Gamma(r_{sp}) = \mathbf{sp} \ w_f \ t_f \ n' \quad \Gamma' = \Gamma[r_{sp} \mapsto \mathbf{sp} \ w_{f'} \ t + 1 \ 0] \quad \mu((w_f, t_f), n') = w_{ret} \quad \mu' = \mathit{local_mem_split}(\mu, (w_f, t_f), (w_{f'}, t + 1), n', n_{copy})}$$

$$\frac{p_{AS} \vdash (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu)}{\rightsquigarrow (((w_f, t_f), w_{ret}, \mathbf{sp} \ w_f \ t_f \ n') :: \delta, (w_{f'}, t + 1), t + 1, w_{f'}, \Gamma', M, \mu')}$$

[ASIR-tailcall]

$$\frac{p_{AS} = \mathbf{prog} \ r_{sp} \ \bar{f} \quad \mathit{func}(p_{AS}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ n_{diff} \ n_{min} \ n_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w_f \ \mathit{cfg} \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{tailcall?} \ b \ n'_{diff} \ n_{copy}) \in \mathit{cfg} \quad \Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w_{f'} \quad \mathit{func}(p_{AS}, w_{f'}) = \mathbf{func} \ n'_{diff} \ n'_{min} \ n'_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w_{f'} \ \mathit{cfg} \quad \Gamma(r_{sp}) = \mathbf{sp} \ w_f \ t_f \ n' \quad \Gamma' = \Gamma[r_{sp} \mapsto \mathbf{sp} \ w_{f'} \ t + 1 \ 0] \quad \mu' = \mathit{local_mem_split}(\mu, (w_f, t_f), (w_{f'}, t + 1), n', n_{copy})}{p_{AS} \vdash (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu)}$$

$$\rightsquigarrow (((w_f, t_f), w_{ret}, \mathbf{sp} \ w_f \ t_f \ n') :: \delta, (w_{f'}, t + 1), t + 1, w_{f'}, \Gamma', M, \mu')$$

[ASIR-ret]

$$\frac{p_{AS} = \mathbf{prog} \ r_{sp} \ \bar{f} \quad \mathit{func}(p_{AS}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ n_{diff} \ n_{min} \ n_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w_f \ \mathit{cfg} \quad \mathit{func}(p_{AS}, w_{f'}) = \mathbf{func} \ n'_{diff} \ n'_{min} \ n'_{max} \ \bar{n}' \ w_{f'} \ \mathit{cfg}' \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{ret}) \in \mathit{cfg}' \quad \Gamma(r_{sp}) = \mathbf{sp} \ w_{f'} \ t_{f'} \ n_{diff} \quad \Gamma' = \Gamma[r_{sp} \mapsto \mathbf{sp} \ w_f \ t_f \ n + n_{diff}] \mu' = \mathit{local_mem_merge}(\mu, (w_f, t_f), (w_{f'}, t_{f'}), n)}{p_{AS} \vdash (((w_f, t_f), w_{ret}, \mathbf{sp} \ w_f \ t_f \ n) :: \delta, (w_{f'}, t_{f'}), t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu) \rightsquigarrow (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{ret}, \Gamma', M, \mu')}$$

$$\frac{\mathit{func}(p_{AS}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ n_{diff} \ n_{min} \ n_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w_f \ \mathit{cfg} \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{fallthrough} \ i \ w) \in \mathit{cfg} \quad p_{AS}, (w_f, t_f), \Gamma, M, \mu + i \Rightarrow \Gamma', M', \mu'}{p_{AS} \vdash (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu) \rightsquigarrow (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w, \Gamma', M', \mu')}$$

[ASIR-branch-true]

$$\frac{p_{AS} = \mathbf{prog} \ r_{sp} \ \bar{f} \quad \mathit{func}(p_{AS}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ n_{diff} \ n_{min} \ n_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w_f \ \mathit{cfg} \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{branch?} \ b \ w_1 \ w_2) \in \mathit{cfg} \quad \Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w \quad w \neq \mathbf{undef} \quad w \neq 0}{p_{AS} \vdash (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu) \rightsquigarrow (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_1, \Gamma, M, \mu)}$$

$$\rightsquigarrow (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_1, \Gamma, M, \mu)$$

[ASIR-branch-false]

$$\frac{p_{AS} = \mathbf{prog} \ r_{sp} \ \bar{f} \quad \mathit{func}(p_{AS}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ n_{diff} \ n_{min} \ n_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w_f \ \mathit{cfg} \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{branch?} \ b \ w_1 \ w_2) \in \mathit{cfg} \quad \Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w \quad w = 0}{p_{AS} \vdash (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu) \rightsquigarrow (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_2, \Gamma, M, \mu)}$$

$$\rightsquigarrow (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_2, \Gamma, M, \mu)$$

[ASIR-goto]

$$\frac{p_{AS} = \mathbf{prog} \ r_{sp} \ \bar{f} \quad \mathit{func}(p_{AS}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ n_{diff} \ n_{min} \ n_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w_f \ \mathit{cfg} \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{goto} \ w) \in \mathit{cfg}}{p_{AS} \vdash (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu) \rightsquigarrow (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w, \Gamma, M, \mu)}$$

[ASIR-gotoind]

$$\frac{p_{AS} = \mathbf{prog} \ r_{sp} \ \bar{f} \quad \mathit{func}(p_{AS}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ n_{diff} \ n_{min} \ n_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w_f \ \mathit{cfg} \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{goto_ind?} \ b \ \bar{w}) \in \mathit{cfg} \quad \Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w \quad w \in \bar{w}}{p_{AS} \vdash (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu) \rightsquigarrow (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w, \Gamma, M, \mu)}$$

Fig. 14 (cont.). Small-step semantics of ASIR

define the simulation of two memories if the memory of the target language can be concretized to the memory of the source language. To concretize local memory into the lower-level memory, we need to assign each abstract stack pointer to a concrete address. To describe this, we assume there is a function $\mathit{assign} : \mathcal{W} \rightarrow \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathcal{W}$ that maps abstract stack pointers to concrete addresses.

The function $assign$ satisfies the following constraint: $assign(w_i, t_i) + n_i = assign(w_{i-1}, t_{i-1})$. The constraint means that for each call site, the concretized stack pointer before the call instruction is equal to the concretized stack pointer after the call instruction.

To concretize the local memory, we need to merge the local memory with the global memory to make a whole memory. We define the merging of the local memory with a given stack pointer and boundary as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & mem_merge(w_{sp}, M, \mu, w_f, t_f) = \\
 & \text{let } (n_{min}, n_{max}, M_{local}) = \mu(w_f, t_f) \text{ in} \\
 & \lambda w. \begin{cases} M_{local}(w - w_{sp}) & \text{if } n_{min} \leq w - w_{sp} \leq n_{max} \\ M(w) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

Given the assign function, we define merging all local memories from the call stack recursively as follows:

$$mem_merge_all(M, \mu, (w, t), \overline{(w_i, t_i)}) = mem_merge(assign(w, t), mem_merge_all(M, \mu, \overline{(w_i, t_i)}), w, t)$$

Now we have merged global memory and register files with the target language value. We use the notation $assign_val(M_{AS})$ and $assign_val(\Gamma_{AS})$ to replace all abstract stack pointer values with the concrete address defined by the assignment function.

Now, we can define the simulation relation between the FGIR state and the ASIR state. We first define the simulation between FGIR memory/registers and ASIR memory/registers if there is a $assign$ function that can concretize the ASIR memory/registers to one that is equivalent to the FGIR memory/registers. We define the equivalence between two memories and two register files as follows:

Definition 6.1 (Equivalence between FGIR and ASIR memory and registers.). Given an FGIR memory M and an ASIR memory M' , the equivalence of two memories is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 M \equiv M' & \iff \\
 \forall w, M(w) &= M'(w) \vee M'(w) = \mathbf{undef}
 \end{aligned}$$

where the relation for memory is defined as equality or the value is undefined. The relation for the register file is defined similarly.

Definition 6.2 (Simulation relation between FGIR and ASIR states.). Given an FGIR state $(\delta, w_f, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M)$ and an ASIR state $(\delta', cf, t, w'_{pc}, \Gamma', M', \mu')$, the simulation relation is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (\delta, w_f, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \sim (\delta', cf, t, w'_{pc}, \Gamma', M', \mu') \iff \\
 & \exists assign. \begin{cases} \delta = map(\delta', \lambda((f, t), y, z) \mapsto (f, y)) \\ (w_f, t') = cf \\ w_{pc} = w'_{pc} \\ M \equiv assign_val(mem_merge_all(M', \mu', cf \cdot map(\delta', \lambda((f, t), y, z) \mapsto (f, t)))) \\ \Gamma \equiv assign_val(\Gamma') \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

where the relation for the call stack is defined as equality after replacing the saved stack pointer, and the relation for the register file is defined as register-wise value equality.

We denote the filtering relation as $(r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \supseteq \tau'_{AS}$. The relation is defined inductively by the inference rules in Figure 15.

The rules that make significant changes to target language states are as follows:

[TSU-op]

$$\frac{\text{func}(p_{FG}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ w_f \ \text{cfg} \quad (r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \supseteq \tau'_{AS} \quad \tau'_{AS} = \tau''_{AS} \cdot (\delta, cf, t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu)}{(\underbrace{w_{pc}, \mathbf{fallthrough}(\mathbf{assign} \ r \ e)}_{w_{next}}) \in \text{cfg} \quad \Gamma \vdash e \Downarrow v \quad p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \cdot \sigma} \\ (r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \cdot \sigma \supseteq \tau'_{AS} \cdot (\delta, cf, t, w_{next}, \Gamma[r \mapsto v], M, \mu)$$

[TSU-load-1]

$$\frac{\text{func}(p_{FG}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ w_f \ \text{cfg} \quad (r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \supseteq \tau'_{AS} \quad \tau'_{AS} = \tau''_{AS} \cdot (\delta, cf, t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu)}{(\underbrace{w_{pc}, \mathbf{fallthrough}(\mathbf{load} \ r \ b)}_{w_{next}}) \in \text{cfg} \quad \Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w \quad M(w) = v \quad p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \cdot \sigma} \\ (r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \cdot \sigma \supseteq \tau'_{AS} \cdot (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{next}, \Gamma[r \mapsto v], M, \mu)$$

[TSU-load-2]

$$\frac{\text{func}(p_{FG}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ w_f \ \text{cfg} \quad (r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \supseteq \tau'_{AS} \quad \tau'_{AS} = \tau''_{AS} \cdot (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu)}{(\underbrace{w_{pc}, \mathbf{fallthrough}(\mathbf{load} \ r \ b)}_{w_{next}}) \in \text{cfg} \quad \Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow \mathbf{sp} \ w_f \ t \ n'} \\ \text{f}_{sig}(w_f) = (n_{diff}, n_{min}, n_{max}, N, W, f_{call}) \quad n_{min} \leq n' \leq n_{max} \quad \mu((w_f, t), n') = v \quad p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \cdot \sigma} \\ (r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \cdot \sigma \supseteq \tau'_{AS} \cdot (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{next}, \Gamma[r \mapsto v], M, \mu)$$

[TSU-load-3]

$$\frac{\text{func}(p_{FG}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ w_f \ \text{cfg} \quad (r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \supseteq \tau'_{AS} \quad \tau'_{AS} = \tau''_{AS} \cdot (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu)}{(\underbrace{w_{pc}, \mathbf{load} \ r \ b} \in \text{cfg} \quad \text{f}_{sig}(w_f) = (n_{diff}, n_{min}, n_{max}, N, W, f_{call}) \quad \Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow \mathbf{undef}}_{p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \cdot \sigma} \\ (r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \cdot \sigma \supseteq \tau'_{AS} \cdot (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{next}, \Gamma[r \mapsto \mathbf{undef}], M, \mu)$$

[TSU-store-1]

$$\frac{\text{func}(p_{FG}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ w_f \ \text{cfg} \quad (r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \supseteq \tau'_{AS} \quad \tau'_{AS} = \tau''_{AS} \cdot (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu)}{(\underbrace{w_{pc}, \mathbf{fallthrough}(\mathbf{store} \ b_1 \ b_2)}_{w_{next}}) \in \text{cfg} \quad \Gamma \vdash b_1 \Downarrow w \quad \Gamma \vdash b_2 \Downarrow v \quad p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \cdot \sigma} \\ (r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \cdot \sigma \supseteq \tau'_{AS} \cdot (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{next}, \Gamma, M[w \mapsto v], \mu)$$

[TSU-store-2]

$$\frac{\text{func}(p_{FG}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ w_f \ \text{cfg} \quad (r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \supseteq \tau'_{AS} \quad \tau'_{AS} = \tau''_{AS} \cdot (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu)}{(\underbrace{w_{pc}, \mathbf{fallthrough}(\mathbf{store} \ b_1 \ b_2)}_{w_{next}}) \in \text{cfg} \quad \Gamma \vdash b_1 \Downarrow \mathbf{sp} \ w_{f'} \ t_{f'} \ n' \quad \text{f}_{sig}(w_{f'}) = (n_{diff}, n_{min}, n_{max}, N, W, f_{call}) \quad n_{min} \leq n' \leq n_{max} \\ (n' \in N \wedge w_{pc} \in W) \vee (n' \notin N \wedge w_{pc} \notin W) \quad \mu' = \mu[((w_{f'}, t_{f'}), \mathbf{nate}') \mapsto v] \quad p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \cdot \sigma} \\ (r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \cdot \sigma \supseteq \tau'_{AS} \cdot (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{next}, \Gamma, M, \mu')$$

Fig. 15. Filtering relation from an FGIR trace to an ASIR trace

- [TSU-load-2] is the rule when the load instruction is used to access the local memory. If the evaluation of the address expression is a stack pointer value, then it checks whether the offset is in the interval $[n_{min}, n_{max}]$. If it is, then it updates the register file with the value in the local memory.
- [TSU-load-3] is the rule when the pointer of the load instruction is an undefined value. It updates the register file with the undefined value.
- [TSU-store-2] is the rule when the store instruction is used to access the local memory. It also requires that the accessing offset is in the interval $[n_{min}, n_{max}]$. Moreover, it requires that if the program counter is in the safe address set W , then it can modify the contents of the safe offset set N . Otherwise, it only can modify the contents of the unsafe offset set $[n_{min}, n_{max}] \setminus N$. This restriction is to prevent the modification of the return address and the saved stack pointer by imprecisely analyzed stores.

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{[TSU-single]} \\
\frac{p_{FG} \vdash \langle ([], w_f, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \rangle \quad \Gamma' = \Gamma[r_{sp} \mapsto \mathbf{sp} \ w_f \ 0 \ 0] \quad \mu = \lambda(cf, t). \mathbf{undef}}{(r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \langle ([], w_f, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M) \rangle \supseteq \langle ([], (w_f, 0), 0, w_{pc}, \Gamma', M, \mu) \rangle} \\
\text{[TSU-call]} \\
\frac{\begin{array}{c} \mathit{func}(p_{FG}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ w_f \ \mathit{cfg} \\ (r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \supseteq \tau'_{AS} \quad \tau'_{AS} = \tau'_{AS} \cdot (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu) \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{call?} \ b \ w_{ret}) \in \mathit{cfg} \\ \Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w_{f'} \quad f_{sig}(w_f) = (n_{diff}, n_{min}, n_{max}, N, W, f_{call}) \quad f_{sig}(w_{f'}) = (n'_{diff}, n'_{min}, n'_{max}, N', W', f'_{call}) \\ f_{call}(w_{pc}) = (n'_{diff}, n_{copy}) \quad \Gamma(r_{sp}) = \mathbf{sp} \ w_f \ t_f \ n \quad \Gamma' = \Gamma[r_{sp} \mapsto \mathbf{sp} \ w_{f'} \ t + 1 \ 0] \\ \mu((w_f, t_f), n) = w_{ret} \quad \mu' = \mathit{local_mem_split}(\mu, (w_f, t_f), (w_{f'}, t + 1), n, n_{copy}) \quad p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \cdot \sigma \end{array}}{(r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \cdot \sigma \supseteq \tau'_{AS} \cdot (((w_f, t_f), w_{ret}, \mathbf{sp} \ w_f \ t_f \ n) :: \delta, (w_{f'}, t + 1), t + 1, w_{f'}, \Gamma', M, \mu')} \\
\text{[TSU-tailcall]} \\
\frac{\begin{array}{c} \mathit{func}(p_{FG}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ w_f \ \mathit{cfg} \\ (r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \supseteq \tau'_{AS} \quad \tau'_{AS} = \tau'_{AS} \cdot (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu) \\ (w_{pc}, \mathbf{tailcall?} \ b) \in \mathit{cfg} \quad \Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w_{f'} \quad f_{sig}(w_f) = (n_{diff}, n_{min}, n_{max}, N, W, f_{call}) \\ f_{sig}(w_{f'}) = (n'_{diff}, n'_{min}, n'_{max}, N', W', f'_{call}) \quad f_{call}(w_{pc}) = (n'_{diff}, n_{copy}) \quad \Gamma(r_{sp}) = \mathbf{sp} \ w_f \ t_f \ n \\ \Gamma' = \Gamma[r_{sp} \mapsto \mathbf{sp} \ w_{f'} \ t + 1 \ 0] \quad \mu' = \mathit{local_mem_split}(\mu, (w_f, t_f), (w_{f'}, t + 1), n, n_{copy}) \quad p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \cdot \sigma \end{array}}{(r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \cdot \sigma \supseteq \tau'_{AS} \cdot (\delta, (w_{f'}, t + 1), t + 1, w_{f'}, \Gamma', M, \mu')} \\
\text{[TSU-ret]} \\
\frac{\begin{array}{c} \mathit{func}(p_{FG}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ w_f \ \mathit{cfg} \\ (r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \supseteq \tau'_{AS} \quad \tau'_{AS} = \tau'_{AS} \cdot (((w_f, t_f), w_{ret}, \mathbf{sp} \ w_f \ t_f \ n) :: \delta, (w_{f'}, t_f'), t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu) \\ f_{sig}(w_{f'}) = (n_{diff}, n'_{min}, n'_{max}, N', W', f'_{call}) \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{ret?} \ b) \in \mathit{cfg} \quad \Gamma(r_{sp}) = \mathbf{sp} \ w_{f'} \ t_f' \ n_{diff} \\ \Gamma' = \Gamma[r_{sp} \mapsto \mathbf{sp} \ w_f \ t_f \ n + n_{diff}] \mu' = \mathit{local_mem_merge}(\mu, (w_f, t_f), (w_{f'}, t_f'), n) \quad p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \cdot \sigma \end{array}}{(r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \cdot \sigma \supseteq \tau'_{AS} \cdot (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{ret}, \Gamma', M, \mu')}
\end{array}$$

Fig. 15 (cont.). Filtering relation from an FGIR trace to an ASIR trace

- [TSU-call] is the rule for the call instruction. It first checks that the current stack pointer points to the current local memory. Then, the call stack is updated with the current function, return address, and the stack pointer value. Furthermore, new local memory is allocated by splitting the current local memory using the helper function $\mathit{local_mem_split}$ by the number of bytes to copy from the caller's local memory to the callee's local memory.
- [TSU-ret] is the rule for the return instruction. It uses the top element of the call stack to restore the current function, program counter, and the stack pointer value. Also, it merges the local memory with the local memory of the caller function.

Proof sketch of proposition 4.7. The first property, $(r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \supseteq \tau'_{AS} \Rightarrow p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG}$ is straightforward because all rules of filtering require a valid trace. The second property, $(r_{sp}, f_{sig}), p_{FG} \vdash \tau_{FG} \supseteq \tau'_{AS} \Rightarrow \tau_{FG} \sim \tau'_{AS}$ requires induction. The base case is straightforward because the corresponding states between $([], w_f, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M)$ and $([], (w_f, 0), 0, w_{pc}, \Gamma[r_{sp} \mapsto \mathbf{sp} \ w_f \ 0 \ 0], M, \mu)$ can satisfy the relation by setting the assign function $\mathit{assign}(w_f, 0) = \Gamma(r_{sp})$. For inductive cases, the core cases are [TSU-call] and [TSU-ret]. For [TSU-call] cases, the stack content and local memory created by $\mathit{local_mem_split}$ do not change the whole merged memory for any assignment. For [TSU-ret] cases, the same argument can be applied for the merging of the local memory with $\mathit{local_mem_merge}$. The other cases are straightforward correspondence between the states.

Proof sketch of proposition 4.8. For any trace τ , exactly one rule is applicable to extend the trace. The proof is straightforward by the construction of the rules.

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{[SSU-op]} \\
\frac{(w_{pc}, \mathbf{fallthrough}(\mathbf{assign} \ r \ e) \ w_{next}) \in \mathit{cfg}}{\perp \sqsubset \Gamma_{w_{pc}}^{\#} \Rightarrow \Gamma_{w_{pc}}^{\#} [r \mapsto \mathit{eval}^{\#}(op)(\Gamma_{w_{pc}}^{\#})] \sqsubseteq \Gamma_{w_{next}}^{\#}} \\
\text{[SSU-load]} \\
\frac{(w_{pc}, \mathbf{fallthrough}(\mathbf{load} \ r \ b) \ w_{next}) \in \mathit{cfg}}{(\perp \sqsubset \Gamma_{w_{pc}}^{\#}) \wedge (\mathit{eval}^{\#}(b)(\Gamma_{w_{pc}}^{\#}) \neq (\bar{n}, \mathbf{sp}^{\#} \ n)) \Rightarrow \Gamma_{w_{pc}}^{\#} [r \mapsto \top] \sqsubseteq \Gamma_{w_{next}}^{\#}} \\
(\perp \sqsubset \Gamma_{w_{pc}}^{\#}) \wedge (\mathit{eval}^{\#}(b)(\Gamma_{w_{pc}}^{\#}) = (\bar{n}, \mathbf{sp}^{\#} \ n)) \Rightarrow \Gamma_{w_{pc}}^{\#} [r \mapsto n \cdot \mu_{w_{pc}}^{\#}(n)] \sqsubseteq \Gamma_{w_{next}}^{\#} \\
\text{[SSU-store]} \\
\frac{(w_{pc}, \mathbf{fallthrough}(\mathbf{store} \ b_1 \ b_2) \ w_{next}) \in \mathit{cfg} \quad \Gamma^{\#} \vdash b_1 \Downarrow w}{\perp \sqsubset \Gamma_{w_{pc}}^{\#} \wedge (\mathit{eval}^{\#}(b_1)(\Gamma_{w_{pc}}^{\#}) = (\bar{n}, w)) \Rightarrow \mu_{w_{pc}}^{\#} \sqsubseteq \mu_{w_{next}}^{\#} \quad \perp \sqsubset \Gamma_{w_{pc}}^{\#} \wedge (\mathit{eval}^{\#}(b_1)(\Gamma_{w_{pc}}^{\#}) = (\bar{n}, \mathbf{sp}^{\#} \ n)) \Rightarrow} \\
\frac{(w_{pc} \in \bar{w}) \wedge (\mu_{w_{pc}}^{\#} [n \mapsto \mathit{eval}^{\#}(b_2)(\Gamma_{w_{pc}}^{\#})] \sqsubseteq \mu_{w_{next}}^{\#})}{\text{[SSU-single]} \\
\frac{\top [r_{sp} \mapsto \mathbf{sp}^{\#} \ 0] \sqsubseteq \Gamma_{w_e}^{\#} \quad \top [0 \mapsto \mathbf{ret}^{\#}] \sqsubseteq \mu_{w_e}^{\#}}{\text{[SSU-call]} \\
\frac{\perp \sqsubset \hat{a}_{w_{pc}} \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{call?} \ b \ w_{ret}) \in \mathit{cfg} \quad h(p_{FG}, w_{pc}) = (n_{diff}, n_{copy})}{\Gamma_{w_{pc}}^{\#}(r_{sp}) = (\bar{n}, \mathbf{sp}^{\#} \ n) \Rightarrow [r_{sp} \mapsto \mathbf{sp}^{\#} \ n + n_{diff}] \sqsubseteq \Gamma_{w_{ret}}^{\#}} \\
\text{[SSU-others]} \\
\frac{\perp \sqsubset \hat{a}_{w_{pc}} \quad (w_{pc}, j_{FG}) \in \mathit{cfg} \quad w_{next} \in \mathit{succ}(j_{FG})}{\hat{a}_{w_{pc}} \sqsubseteq \Gamma_{w_{next}}^{\#}}
\end{array}$$

Fig. 16. Abstract stack reconstruction for a single function

6.3 Syntactic Abstract Stack Reconstruction

Static analysis to reconstruct the abstract stack and local memory tracks the value of the stack pointer register, records the maximum/minimum stack access offset, and ensures whether the value of the stack pointer register is the same for all paths to the return instruction. However, it is not tractable to track the precise stack offset for all paths because of inter-procedural control flow. To solve this problem, we record safe stack access offsets N , which denote that the stack offset in this set is not modified by imprecisely analyzed stores. We use the safe stack access offset *per* each register and stack offset during analysis, and then fix a single safe set required to ensure that the return address value and saved stack pointer are preserved.

The analysis result \hat{a} is a triple of safe addresses \bar{w} , abstract register file $\Gamma^{\#}$, and abstract local memory $\mu^{\#}$ for each function. We define the abstract state, abstract register file, abstract local memory, and abstract value as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{a} &::= (\bar{w}, \Gamma^{\#}, \mu^{\#}) \\
\Gamma^{\#} &::= \{r \mapsto (\bar{n}, v^{\#})\} \cup \{\top\} \\
\mu^{\#} &::= \{n \mapsto (\bar{n}, v^{\#})\} \cup \{\top\} \\
v^{\#} &::= \top \mid w \mid \mathbf{sp}^{\#} \ n \mid \mathbf{ret}^{\#}
\end{aligned}$$

When $\hat{a} = (\bar{w}, \Gamma^{\#}, \mu^{\#})$ and $\Gamma^{\#}(r) = (\bar{n}, v^{\#})$, if \bar{w} contains all the addresses of the instructions that store values at the local memory offsets in \bar{n} from the beginning of the program, then $v^{\#}$ denotes the values of the current register r . The same principle applies to $\mu^{\#}$.

The inference rules in Figure 16 define the static analysis for the single function **func** w_e *cfg*. The rules are divided into two parts: the first part is for instructions and the second part is for jumps. We use a helper function eval^\sharp to evaluate the expression to an abstract value, where $\text{eval}^\sharp(r)(\Gamma^\sharp) = \Gamma^\sharp(r)$ and $\text{eval}^\sharp(w)(\Gamma^\sharp) = ([], w)$. The core of the analysis is [SSU-load], [SSU-store], and [SSU-call]. The first constraint of [SSU-load] describes the situation in which the load address is not related to the stack. The second constraint describes if the load address is an abstract stack pointer, then look up the abstract value at abstract local memory and assign it with appending the current offset as a requirement of safe offset set to retrieve the value. The rule for stores is similar, but it should update the safe addresses when the store address is precisely evaluated. The example is as follows.

```

1   assign r_1 (r_sp + 4)
2   store 3 r_1
3   store 100 r_2
4   load r_3 r_1

```

Suppose the abstract register file contains a top value for each register except for the stack pointer register, which is $([], \mathbf{sp}^\sharp 0)$ at the beginning. At line 4, the analysis result of the abstract register file is $[r_1 \mapsto ([], \mathbf{sp}^\sharp 4), r_2 \mapsto \top, r_3 \mapsto ([4], 3)]$, and the abstract local memory is $[4 \mapsto ([], 3)]$ and the safe address set is $[2]$. This is because the store of line 3 is not considered a safe access to the stack.

The call rule [SSU-call] simply updates the stack pointer register with the difference from the stack pointer given by the heuristic function h .

After the function-wise analysis, we can obtain a safe address set \bar{w} , an abstract register file Γ^\sharp , and an abstract local memory μ^\sharp per each function. We choose the assumptions $(n_{diff}, n_{min}, n_{max}, N, W)$ as follows:

- n_{diff} is the value of the abstract stack pointer of r_{sp} for each return instruction.
- n_{min} and n_{max} are the minimum and maximum offsets from the abstract local memory μ^\sharp .
- N is the union of all safe offsets in $\Gamma^\sharp(r_{sp})$ and $\mu^\sharp(0)$ for all return instructions.
- W is \bar{w} .

6.4 ASIR transformation

The transformation from FGIR to ASIR is defined in Figure 17. The transformation is divided into three parts: an instruction-wise transformation \mathcal{T}_i , a function-wise transformation \mathcal{T}_f , and a whole program transformation T . The function-wise transformation adds the function signature to the ASIR function. The instruction-wise transformation maps each FGIR instruction to its corresponding ASIR instruction. Most instructions are mapped directly to the corresponding ASIR instruction. The transformation of **call?**, **tailcall?** only requires the assumptions. The transformation of **load**, **store** requires the assumption and the abstract state to decide the pointer value and whether the memory access can be considered safe local access. If it is safe local access, it is transformed to **lload**, **lstore**, otherwise, it is transformed to **load?**, **store?**. For other instructions, the transformation is the identity function.

Proof sketch of proposition 4.9. Suppose the ASIR trace is extended by a single step. As same as FGIR-to-ILIR transformation, almost all rules of small step semantics of ASIR except [ASIR-lstore], [ASIR-lload] have the same premises as the corresponding filtering rules of FGIR. For [ASIR-lstore], [ASIR-lload], we can use the definition of transformation and property of sound analysis to ensure that if the abstract register value is $\mathbf{sp}^\sharp n$, then the actual value is also $\mathbf{sp} w_f t_f n$ for current function w_f and the current tick t_f . Also, the minimum and maximum of the stack offset are determined by

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{T}_f((r_{sp}, (n_{diff}, n_{min}, n_{max}, N, W, f_{call})), \mathbf{func} \ w \ (\overline{w_x}, \overline{j_x}), \overline{\Gamma^\#}) = \\
& \quad \mathbf{func} \ n_{diff} \ n_{min} \ n_{max} \ w \ (w_x, \mathcal{T}_i((r_{sp}, (N, W, f_{call})), j_x, \Gamma_{w_x}^\#)) \\
& \mathcal{T}_j((r_{sp}, (N, W, (n_{diff}, n_{copy}))), j, \Gamma^\#) = \\
& \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \mathbf{fallthrough} \ \mathcal{T}_i((r_{sp}, (N, W)), i, \Gamma^\#) \ w & \text{if } i = \mathbf{fallthrough} \ i \ w \\ \mathbf{call?} \ b \ n_{diff} \ n_{copy} \ w_{ret} & \text{if } i = \mathbf{call?} \ b \ w_{ret} \\ \mathbf{tailcall?} \ b \ n_{diff} \ n_{copy} & \text{if } i = \mathbf{tailcall?} \ b \\ \mathbf{ret} & \text{if } i = \mathbf{ret?} \ b \ \wedge \ \Gamma^\#(b) = (_, \mathbf{ret}^\#) \\ j & \text{otherwise} \end{array} \right. \\
& \mathcal{T}_i((r_{sp}, (N, W)), i, \Gamma^\#) = \\
& \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \mathbf{load?} \ r \ b & \text{if } i = \mathbf{load} \ r \ b \ \wedge \ \Gamma^\#(b) = (_, \top) \\ \mathbf{lload} \ r \ n & \text{if } i = \mathbf{load} \ r \ b \ \wedge \ \Gamma^\#(b) = (_, \mathbf{sp}^\# \ n) \\ \mathbf{store?} \ b_1 \ b_2 & \text{if } i = \mathbf{store} \ b_1 \ b_2 \ \wedge \ w_{pc} \notin W \ \vee \ \Gamma^\#(b_1) = (_, \top) \\ \mathbf{lstore} \ b_1 \ b_2 & \text{if } i = \mathbf{store} \ b_1 \ b_2 \ \wedge \ w_{pc} \in W \ \wedge \ \Gamma^\#(b_1) = (_, \mathbf{sp}^\# \ n) \\ i & \text{otherwise} \end{array} \right.
\end{aligned}$$

Fig. 17. ASIR transformation

the abstract register, so if the abstract register value is $\mathbf{sp}^\# \ n$ then $n_{min} \leq n \leq n_{max}$ for the current function. Therefore, the FGIR trace is also extended by a single step if the ASIR trace is extended by a single step.

We omit the proof sketch of Proposition 4.10 because the reasoning is similar to the proof of Proposition 4.9, by case analysis of the FGIR filtering rules.

7 Function Input/Output Identification

The first two transformations provide a call stack with saved stack pointer registers and return addresses. However, registers other than the stack pointer are still used across function boundaries. To address this, we examined IRs that annotate input/output registers for functions, such as RetDec [7], Ghidra [2], and IDA Pro [49], and captured their core concepts in the Input-Output IR (IOIR).

7.1 Input-Output IR (IOIR)

For a function, its input registers denote the registers that make the function's behavior different, and its output registers denote the registers that the function changes. The input/output registers of a function depend on the input/output registers of the functions being called in the function body. Since call targets are not always statically known, we assume a call signature for each call site to identify the input/output of the function being called.

The syntax of IOIR is defined in Figure 18a. IOIR annotates the input and saved registers for each function definition and call site. The IOIR syntax is similar to ASIR, except for the function definition and the call instruction. The function definition $\mathbf{func} \ n_{diff} \ n_{min} \ n_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w \ (\overline{w}, \overline{j_{IR}}) \ \overline{r_{in}} \ \overline{r_{saved}}$ additionally has the input and saved registers for the function. Also, the call instruction $\mathbf{call?} \ b \ n \ n \ \overline{r_{in}} \ \overline{r_{saved}} \ w$ additionally has the input and saved registers for the call target.

The definition of the value and the state of IOIR is shown in Figure 13b. In IOIR value, we introduce an opaque value $\mathbf{reg} \ r$ which represents the value of the register r at the start of the function. The opaque value is used to check the assumption of the saved register at the return instruction.

p_{IO}	:	IOIR Program	j_{IO}	::=	call? $b \ n \ n \ \overline{r_{in}} \ \overline{r_{saved}} \ w$
p_{IO}	::=	prog $r \ \overline{f_{IO}}$			tailcall? $b \ n \ n \ \overline{r_{in}} \ \overline{r_{saved}}$
\hat{f}_{IO}	::=	func $n_{diff} \ n_{min} \ n_{max} \ \overline{n} \ w \ \overline{(w, j_{IO})} \ \overline{r_{in}} \ \overline{r_{saved}}$			ret
i_{IO}	::=	assign $r \ e$			fallthrough $i_{IO} \ w$
		load? $r \ b$			branch? $b \ w \ w$
		store? $b \ b$			goto w
		load $r \ n$			goto_ind? $b \ \overline{w}$
		lstore $b \ n$			
		nop			

(a) Syntax

v	::=	w	Γ	::=	$r \mapsto v$
		undef			$M ::= w \mapsto v$
		sp $f \ t \ n$			$\mu ::= cf \mapsto (n_{min}, n_{max}, (n \mapsto v))$
		reg r			$cf ::= \frac{(w_f, t_f)}{(cf, w_{ret}, \Gamma)}$
t	\in	$\mathbf{T} = \mathbb{N}$	cf	::=	$\frac{(w_f, t_f)}{(cf, w_{ret}, \Gamma)}$
σ	::=	$(\delta, cf, t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu)$	δ	::=	(cf, w_{ret}, Γ)

(b) State

Fig. 18. Syntax and state of IOIR

An IOIR state is a 7-tuple $(\delta, f, t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu)$. The only difference from an ASIR state is the call stack. The call stack is a list of tuples $(cf, w_{ret}, \Gamma_{saved})$. In this language, the call stack saves values of a collection of registers Γ_{saved} , instead of a single register r_{sp} as in the previous language.

The small-step semantics of IOIR is defined in Figure 19. We omit the rules for the instructions and intra-procedural jumps since they are the same as those in ASIR. The rules for the call, tail-call, and return instructions are different from ASIR. We introduce helper functions to split and merge register files, $local_regs_split$ and $local_regs_merge$ respectively.

For a given register file Γ , input registers $\overline{r_{in}}$, and saved registers $\overline{r_{saved}}$, the function $local_regs_split(\Gamma, \overline{r_{in}}, \overline{r_{saved}})$ returns two register files Γ' and Γ_{saved} . The first one is used to pass the input registers to the call target, and the second one is used to save the registers that are not input registers. The function $local_regs_merge(\Gamma, \Gamma_{saved})$ merges the saved registers back to the register file. These two functions are formally defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 local_regs_split(\Gamma, \overline{r_{in}}, \overline{r_{saved}}) &= (\Gamma', \Gamma_{saved}) \\
 \text{where} \quad \Gamma' &= \lambda r. \text{ if } r \in \overline{r_{in}} \text{ then } \Gamma(r) \text{ else } \mathbf{reg} \ r \\
 \Gamma_{saved} &= \lambda r. \text{ if } r \in \overline{r_{saved}} \text{ then } \Gamma(r) \text{ else } \mathbf{undef} \\
 local_regs_merge(\Gamma, \Gamma_{saved}) &= \lambda r. \text{ if } \Gamma(r) = \mathbf{reg} \ r \text{ then } \Gamma_{saved}(r) \text{ else } \Gamma(r)
 \end{aligned}$$

With these helper functions, the rules for the call, tail-call, and return instructions are defined as follows:

- [IOIR-call] is the rule that searches the call signature $\overline{r_{in}}'$ and $\overline{r_{saved}}'$ for the call target. The rule then splits the current register file Γ into the input registers and the saved registers using $local_regs_split(\Gamma, \overline{r_{in}}', \overline{r_{saved}}')$. Then, the rule replaces the current register file with the input register file with updated stack pointer Γ_{in} and pushes the current function, the return address, and the saved register file Γ_{saved} to the call stack.

$$\boxed{p_{IO} \vdash \sigma \rightsquigarrow \sigma'}$$

[IOIR-call]

$$\begin{array}{l}
p_{IO} = \mathbf{prog} \ r_{sp} \ \bar{f} \\
func(p_{IO}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ n_{diff} \ n_{min} \ n_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w_f \ cfg \ \bar{r}_{in} \ \bar{r}_{saved} \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{call?} \ b \ n'_{diff} \ n_{copy} \ w_{ret} \ \bar{r}'_{in} \ \bar{r}'_{saved}) \in cfg \\
\Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w_{f'} \quad func(p_{IO}, w_{f'}) = \mathbf{func} \ n'_{diff} \ n'_{min} \ n'_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w_{f'} \ cfg' \ \bar{r}'_{in} \ \bar{r}'_{saved} \quad \Gamma(r_{sp}) = \mathbf{sp} \ w_f \ t_f \ n' \\
\mu((w_f, t_f), n') = w_{ret} \quad \mu' = \mathbf{local_mem_split}(\mu, (w_f, t_f), (w_{f'}, t+1), n', n_{copy}) \\
r_{sp} \in \bar{r}'_{in} \quad r_{sp} \in \bar{r}'_{saved} \quad (\Gamma, \Gamma_{saved}) = \mathbf{local_regs_split}(\Gamma, \bar{r}'_{in}, \bar{r}'_{saved}) \quad \Gamma_{in} = \Gamma'[r_{sp} \mapsto \mathbf{sp} \ w_{f'} \ t+1 \ 0] \\
p_{IO} \vdash (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu) \rightsquigarrow (((w_f, t_f), w_{ret}, \Gamma_{saved}) :: \delta, (w_{f'}, t+1), t+1, w, \Gamma_{in}, M, \mu') \\
\text{[IOIR-tailcall]}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
p_{IO} = \mathbf{prog} \ r_{sp} \ \bar{f} \\
func(p_{IO}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ n_{diff} \ n_{min} \ n_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w_f \ cfg \ \bar{r}_{in} \ \bar{r}_{saved} \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{tailcall?} \ b \ n'_{diff} \ n_{copy} \ \bar{r}'_{in} \ \bar{r}'_{saved}) \in cfg \\
\Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w_{f'} \quad func(p_{IO}, w_{f'}) = \mathbf{func} \ n'_{diff} \ n'_{min} \ n'_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w_{f'} \ \bar{r}'_{in} \ \bar{r}'_{saved} \ cfg' \\
\Gamma(r_{sp}) = \mathbf{sp} \ w_f \ t_f \ n' \quad \mu' = \mathbf{local_mem_split}(\mu, (w_f, t_f), (w_{f'}, t+1), n', n_{copy}) \\
r_{sp} \in \bar{r}'_{in} \quad r_{sp} \in \bar{r}'_{saved} \quad \forall r, \Gamma_{saved}(r) \neq \mathbf{undef} \Rightarrow \Gamma(r) = \mathbf{reg} \ r_{saved} \\
(\Gamma', _) = \mathbf{local_regs_split}(\Gamma, \bar{r}'_{in}, \bar{r}'_{saved}) \quad \Gamma_{in} = \Gamma'[r_{sp} \mapsto \mathbf{sp} \ w_{f'} \ t+1 \ 0] \\
\hline
p_{IO} \vdash ((w_{f'}, w_{ret}, \Gamma_{saved}) :: \delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu) \\
\rightsquigarrow ((w_{f'}, w_{ret}, \Gamma_{saved}) :: \delta, (w_{f'}, t+1), t+1, w, \Gamma_{in}, M, \mu') \\
\text{[IOIR-ret]}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
p_{IO} = \mathbf{prog} \ r_{sp} \ \bar{f} \quad func(p_{IO}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ n_{diff} \ n_{min} \ n_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w_f \ cfg \ \bar{r}_{in} \ \bar{r}_{saved} \\
func(p_{IO}, w_{f'}) = \mathbf{func} \ n'_{diff} \ n'_{min} \ n'_{max} \ \bar{n}' \ w_{f'} \ cfg' \ \bar{r}'_{in} \ \bar{r}'_{saved} \\
(w_{pc}, \mathbf{ret}) \in cfg' \ \mu' = \mathbf{local_mem_merge}(\mu, (w_f, t_f), (w_{f'}, t_{f'}), n) \\
\forall r, \Gamma_{saved}(r) \neq \mathbf{undef} \Rightarrow \Gamma(r) = \mathbf{reg} \ r_{saved} \quad \Gamma' = \mathbf{local_regs_merge}(\Gamma, \Gamma_{saved}) \\
\hline
p_{IO} \vdash (((w_f, t_f), w_{ret}, \Gamma_{saved}) :: \delta, (w_{f'}, t_{f'}), t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu) \rightsquigarrow (\delta, (f, t_f), t, w_{ret}, \Gamma', M, \mu')
\end{array}$$

Fig. 19. Small-step semantics of IOIR

- [IOIR-tailcall] is similar to [IOIR-call] except that it does not push to the call stack, and checks that the assumed saved register is preserved. The premise $\forall r, \Gamma_{saved}(r) \neq \mathbf{undef} \Rightarrow \Gamma(r) = \mathbf{reg} \ r_{saved}$ checks the assumption.
- [IOIR-ret] is the rule for the return instruction. It also checks the assumption that the assumed saved registers are preserved. The rule then merges the saved registers back to the register file using $\mathbf{local_regs_merge}(\Gamma, \Gamma_{saved})$.

7.2 Simulation Relation and Filtering Relation from ASIR to IOIR

To identify the input and output registers of functions, we need to identify the call signature f_{sig} for each call site. A call signature is a function that takes the address of a call instruction and returns (R_{in}, R_{saved}) , where R_{in} is a set of input registers and R_{saved} is a set of saved registers. The saved registers are the registers that are not changed by the function. Then, we can express the output registers as $R_{out} = \mathbb{R} \setminus R_{saved}$.

As we did in the previous section, we define the concretization of the saved registers into a single, merged register file. We define $\mathbf{regs_merge_all}(\Gamma, \delta)$ as the merged register file of the global register file and the saved register files in the call stack. The function $\mathbf{regs_merge_all}$ is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{regs_merge_all}(\Gamma, (cf, w_{ret}, \Gamma_{saved}) \cdot \delta) = \mathbf{regs_merge_all}(\mathbf{local_regs_merge}(\Gamma, \Gamma_{saved}), \delta)$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{[TRU-single]} \\
\frac{p_{AS} \vdash \langle ([], cf, t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu) \rangle}{f_{sig}, p_{AS} \vdash \langle ([], cf, t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu) \rangle \supseteq \langle ([], cf, t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu) \rangle} \\
\text{[TRU-call]} \\
\frac{
\begin{array}{l}
f_{sig}, p_{AS} \vdash \tau_{AS} \supseteq \tau'_{IO} \quad \tau'_{AS} = \tau''_{IO} \cdot (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu) \quad p_{AS} = \mathbf{prog} \ r_{sp} \ \bar{f} \\
(w_{pc}, \mathbf{call?} \ b \ n'_{diff} \ n_{copy} \ w_{ret}) \in \mathit{cfg} \quad \Gamma \vdash b \Downarrow w_{f'} \quad \mathit{func}(p_{AS}, w_{f'}) = \mathbf{func} \ n'_{diff} \ n'_{min} \ n'_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w_{f'} \ \mathit{cfg}' \\
f_{sig}(w_{f'}) = (\overline{r'_{in}}, \overline{r'_{saved}}) \quad \Gamma(r_{sp}) = \mathbf{sp} \ w_f \ t_f \ n' \quad \mu((w_f, t_f), n') = w_{ret} \\
\mu' = \mathit{local_mem_split}(\mu, (w_f, t_f), (w_{f'}, t+1), n', n_{copy}) \quad r_{sp} \in \overline{r'_{in}} \quad r_{sp} \in \overline{r'_{saved}} \\
(\Gamma', \Gamma_{saved}) = \mathit{local_regs_split}(\Gamma, r'_{in}, r'_{saved}) \quad \Gamma_{in} = \Gamma' [r_{sp} \mapsto \mathbf{sp} \ w_{f'} \ t + 1 \ 0] \quad p_{AS} \vdash \tau_{AS} \cdot \sigma
\end{array}
}{
\begin{array}{l}
f_{sig}, p_{AS} \vdash \tau_{AS} \cdot \sigma \supseteq \tau'_{IO} \cdot ((w_f, t_f), w_{ret}, \Gamma_{saved}) :: \delta, (w_{f'}, t+1), t+1, w, \Gamma_{in}, M, \mu' \\
\text{[TRU-ret]} \\
\begin{array}{l}
f_{sig}, p_{AS} \vdash \tau_{AS} \supseteq \tau'_{IO} \\
\tau'_{IO} = \tau''_{IO} \cdot (((w_f, t_f), w_{ret}, \Gamma_{saved}) :: \delta, (w_{f'}, t_f), t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu) \quad p_{AS} = \mathbf{prog} \ r_{sp} \ \bar{f} \\
\mathit{func}(p_{AS}, w_f) = \mathbf{func} \ n_{diff} \ n_{min} \ n_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w_f \ \mathit{cfg}' \quad \mathit{func}(p_{AS}, w_{f'}) = \mathbf{func} \ n'_{diff} \ n'_{min} \ n'_{max} \ \bar{n}' \ w_{f'} \ \mathit{cfg}' \\
(w_{pc}, \mathbf{ret}) \in \mathit{cfg}' \quad \mu' = \mathit{local_mem_merge}(\mu, (w_f, t_f), (w_{f'}, t_f), n) \\
\forall r, \Gamma_{saved}(r) \neq \mathbf{undef} \Rightarrow \Gamma(r) = \mathbf{reg} \ r_{saved} \quad \Gamma' = \mathit{local_regs_merge}(\Gamma, \Gamma_{saved}) \quad p_{AS} \vdash \tau_{AS} \cdot \sigma
\end{array}
\end{array}
}{
f_{sig}, p_{AS} \vdash \tau_{AS} \cdot \sigma \supseteq \tau'_{IO} \cdot (\delta, (w_f, t_f), t, w_{ret}, \Gamma', M, \mu')
}
\end{array}$$

Fig. 20. Filtering relation from an ASIR trace to an IOIR trace

Now, we define the simulation relation between the ASIR and IOIR states if the saved stack pointer is the same in both call stacks and other registers are the same in the ASIR register file and the IOIR merged register file.

Definition 7.1 (Simulation relation between ASIR and IOIR states.) Given a ASIR state $(\delta, cf, t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu)$ and an IOIR state $(\delta', cf', t', w'_{pc}, \Gamma', M', \mu')$, the simulation relation is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
& (\delta, cf, t, w_{pc}, \Gamma, M, \mu) \sim (\delta', cf', t', w'_{pc}, \Gamma', M', \mu') \iff \\
& cf = cf' \wedge t = t' \wedge w_{pc} = w'_{pc} \wedge M = M' \wedge \mu = \mu' \\
& \delta = \mathit{map}(\delta', \lambda(cf, w_{ret}, \Gamma_{saved}). (cf, w_{ret}, \Gamma_{saved}(r_{sp}))) \wedge \\
& \Gamma = \mathit{regs_merge_all}(\Gamma', \delta')
\end{aligned}$$

We denote the filtering relation as $f_{sig}, p_{AS} \vdash \tau_{AS} \supseteq \tau'_{IO}$. The filtering relation is defined by the inference rules in Figure 21. The core rules are [TRU-call] and [TRU-ret]. For the call instruction, the rule [TRU-call] splits the registers into Γ' and Γ_{saved} by the call signature given by f_{sig} and pushes the saved registers into the call stack. For the return instruction, the rule [TRU-ret] merges the saved registers into the register file and pops the saved registers from the call stack. We enforce the stack pointer register r_{sp} to be in the saved registers for the call signature.

Proof sketch of proposition 4.7 and proposition 4.8. The proof of Proposition 4.7 is straightforward by the definition of the simulation relation and the filtering relation because the modification of the register files uses only $\mathit{local_regs_merge}$ and $\mathit{local_regs_split}$, which does not affect the result of $\mathit{regs_merge_all}$. The proof of Proposition 4.8 is also straightforward by the definition of the filtering relation because there is only one rule that can be applied to the trace determined by the last state of the trace.

7.3 Syntactic Function Input/Output Identification

To find input/output registers, we perform a syntactic analysis of the program. For each function, the analysis generates $R_{in, w}$, $R_{saved, w}$, R_{f-in} , and $R_{f-saved}$, which represent input registers for each address

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{[SRU-op]} \\
\frac{(w_{pc}, \mathbf{assign} \ r \ e) \in \text{cfg} \quad \text{regs}(e) = \bar{r}}{R_{in, w_{pc}} \cup \bar{r} \subseteq R_{in, w_{pc+1}} \quad R_{saved, w_{pc+1}} \subseteq R_{saved, w_{pc}} \setminus \{r\}} \\
\text{[SRU-call]} \\
\frac{(w_{pc}, \mathbf{call?} \ b \ n_{diff} \ n_{copy} \ w_{ret}) \in \text{cfg} \quad h(p_{AS}, w_{pc}) = \overline{r_{in}}, \overline{r_{saved}}}{R_{saved, w_{ret}} \subseteq R_{saved, w_{pc}} \cap \overline{r_{saved}} \quad R_{in, w_{pc}} \cup \overline{r_{in}} \subseteq R_{in, w_{ret}}} \\
\text{[SRU-ret]} \\
\frac{\perp \sqsubset R_{in, w_{pc}} \quad (w_{pc}, \mathbf{ret}) \in \text{cfg}}{R_{f-in} \subseteq R_{in, w_{pc}} \quad R_{saved, w_{pc}} \subseteq R_{f-saved}}
\end{array}$$

Fig. 21. Function input/output identification for a single function

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}_f(f_{sig}, \mathbf{func} \ n_{diff} \ n_{min} \ n_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w_f \ (\overline{w_x}, \overline{j_x}), (\overline{r_{in}}, \overline{r_{saved}})) &= \\
\mathbf{func} \ n_{diff} \ n_{min} \ n_{max} \ \bar{n} \ w_f \ (\overline{w_x}, \mathcal{T}_i(f_{sig}(\overline{w_x}), \overline{j_x})) \ \overline{r_{in}} \ \overline{r_{saved}} & \\
\mathcal{T}_i((\overline{r_{in}}, \overline{r_{saved}}), j) &= \\
\begin{cases} \mathbf{call?} \ b \ n_{diff} \ n_{copy} \ w_{ret} \ \overline{r_{in}} \ \overline{r_{saved}} & \text{if } j = \mathbf{call?} \ b \ n_{diff} \ n_{copy} \ w_{ret} \\ \mathbf{tailcall?} \ b \ n_{diff} \ n_{copy} \ \overline{r_{in}} \ \overline{r_{saved}} & \text{if } j = \mathbf{tailcall?} \ b \ n_{diff} \ n_{copy} \\ j & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}
\end{aligned}$$

Fig. 22. IOIR transformation

w , saved registers for each address w , input registers for the function, and saved registers for the function, respectively.

The inference rules in Figure 21 define the static analysis for the single function $\mathbf{func} \ w_e \ \text{cfg}$. We use a helper function $\text{regs}(e)$ to extract the registers used in the operation e . The analysis is performed by traversing the instructions of the function and updating the input/saved register sets. The core of the analysis is the inference rules [SRU-op], [SRU-call], and [SRU-ret].

- [SRU-op]: For an assignment instruction $\mathbf{assign} \ r \ e$, the input registers of the next instruction $R_{in, w_{pc+1}}$ contain the input registers of the current instruction $R_{in, w_{pc}}$ and the registers used in the operation $\text{regs}(e)$.
- [SRU-call]: For a call instruction, the saved registers at return $R_{saved, w_{ret}}$ are contained in the intersection of the saved registers at the current state $R_{saved, w_{pc}}$ and the saved registers of the call target $\overline{r_{saved}}$. The input registers at the return $R_{in, w_{ret}}$ contain the union of the input registers at the current state $R_{in, w_{pc}}$ and the input registers of the call target $\overline{r_{in}}$.
- [SRU-ret]: For a return instruction, the input registers of the function R_{f-in} contain input registers at the current state $R_{in, w_{pc}}$, and the saved registers of the function $R_{f-saved}$ are contained in the saved registers at the current state $R_{saved, w_{pc}}$.

Whole program analysis is performed by combining the result of function-wise analysis for each function in the program. We traverse functions in reverse topological order, so the analysis can refer to the input/saved register sets of the known call targets.

7.4 IOIR transformation

The transformation from ASIR to IOIR is defined in Figure 22. The IOIR transformation is defined as a function \mathcal{T}_f that takes a call information of the function f_{sig} , an ASIR function f_{AS} , and an

analysis result $(\overline{r}_{in}, \overline{r}_{saved})$, and returns an IOIR function f_{IO} . The analysis result is directly annotated to the IOIR function. The instruction of the function is transformed by \mathcal{T}_i , which decorates the call instructions with the f_{sig} .

8 x86-64 Binary Lifter Implementation

We implement a prototype of our approach, named `FIBLE`, to lift x86-64 linux binary program to FGIR, ASIR, and IOIR. `FIBLE` takes an x86-64 binary executable with a list of addresses for the entry points of the functions to be lifted. We use Ghidra to get ILIR and implement the subsequent analysis and transformations in §5 to 7 in OCaml. For each IR, we also implement an interpreter and a checker to verify relevant simulation relations.

8.1 Ghidra P-Code to ILIR

Ghidra analyzes binary executables and generates P-Code, an intermediate representation (IR) to represent the semantics of each instruction. Using the Ghidra API, we extract P-Code for each instruction and convert it to ILIR. We rely on Ghidra solely for generating ILIR and do not utilize its analysis or transformation features.

8.2 CFG Reconstruction

For CFG reconstruction, we design a heuristic function and the analysis functions $post^\#$ and $succ^\#$ described in §5.4 to analyze the intra-procedural control flow of ILIR. We make the heuristics to identify the category of the x86-64 jump instructions. The basic principle is to simply check the mnemonic of the instructions, such as `je`, `jne`, `call`, `ret`, etc. Additionally, we check if a jump target is one of the function entry points to identify tail calls.

For value analysis needed to determine the targets of indirect jumps, we use an abstract interpretation that approximates variable values and relationships through abstract domains, allowing for efficient analysis without requiring exact values.

We apply several abstract domains to analyze it. The octagon domain [40] captures linear relationships between registers (e.g., $rax - rdi \leq 10$) to track inequalities, while the interval domain handles ranges of register values. The congruence domain captures values modulo a constant, useful for pointers or offsets, and the set domain tracks specific sets of concrete values. Combining these domains using a technique called reduced product refines the analysis for greater precision.

To handle conditional branches, we use a power domain [17, 25] that combines the boolean and octagon domains. The boolean power domain tracks register relationships for both true and false outcomes of a condition. For each branch, the analysis splits into two cases and maintains distinct register relationships for both, then merges them when paths rejoin, avoiding the path explosion problem common in symbolic execution.

For efficiency, we perform a pre-analysis to identify registers involved in indirect jumps or function calls, focusing on instructions affecting these registers. The successor function computes the next instruction address or possible jump targets based on value analysis, streamlining the process by targeting relevant instructions.

We do not analyze indirect call target because it is not necessary for CFG reconstruction.

8.3 Abstract Stack Reconstruction

For abstract stack reconstruction, we fix `rsp` as a stack pointer register and design a heuristic function to guess the stack pointer differences for callees. The heuristic function determines the stack pointer differences and the depths of the stack copy; we use the following heuristics:

Table 1. The numbers of binaries passed for each IR, out of the total number of binaries.

Dataset	# Total	# FGIR passed	# ASIR passed	# IOIR passed
Coreutils	37	37 (100.0 %)	32 (86.5 %)	32 (86.5 %)
CGC	44	41 (93.2 %)	31 (70.5 %)	31 (70.5 %)

- We perform a bottom-up analysis so that we can propagate the stack pointer difference n_{diff} and the minimum stack offset access n_{min} from callees to their callers at direct call instructions.
- For indirect call instructions, we fix n_{diff} to 0 and n_{min} to the negative of the current stack pointer value to ensure that the full stack space above the offset of the saved return address is available.

For analysis, we implement the abstraction of only selected instructions precisely: move, linear arithmetic such as addition and subtraction, and memory access instructions. For the other instructions, we simply return the top value.

8.4 Function Input/Output Identification

For function input/output identification, we design a heuristic function to guess the input/output registers for callees. Like the abstract stack reconstruction, we use a bottom-up analysis to propagate the input/output registers from callees to their callers at direct call instructions. For indirect call instructions, we assume to follow the x86-64 System V AMD64 ABI, which utilizes the registers `rdi`, `rsi`, `rdx`, `rcx`, `r8`, and `r9` for integer arguments (and `XMM0` through `XMM7` for floating-point arguments). Additionally, globally used registers like `FS` are treated as input registers, with `rax` serving as the output register.

8.5 Interpreter

We implemented an interpreter for ILIR, ASIR, and IOIR to execute programs and verify the simulation relations between their states. Running the interpreter across all three IRs allows us to check if the filtering relation holds. During execution, for each pair of low-level and high-level states, the interpreter checks if the register and memory values are related, or if the high-level IR state is undefined. An error is raised only if the simulation relation is violated or if only the low-level IR state is undefined (see the definition of filtered-simulation in Definition 4.3).

9 Evaluation

We evaluate our prototype implementation, FIBLE, with the following research questions:

- RQ1) Expressiveness.** Can our IRs represent valid binaries generated by a standard compiler?
RQ2) Correctness. Does our implementation satisfy filtered-simulation?
RQ3) Performance. Are our transformations fast enough to lift binaries?

Our evaluation distinguishes between expressiveness and correctness. Expressiveness examines how well our IR captures real-world binary execution, while correctness ensures that our implementation accurately lifts binaries according to the filtered-simulation relation. Additionally, we evaluate performance to verify that our transformations are fast enough for practical use.

9.1 Experimental Setup

9.1.1 Datasets. We use two datasets for evaluation: the Coreutils dataset and the CGC dataset. The Coreutils dataset is a collection of basic utilities for Unix-like systems, commonly found in Linux distributions. We use it to demonstrate real-world binary lifting. Moreover, we use the CGC

dataset, provided by DARPA, to evaluate the expressiveness of our lifted code in handling various C features. The CGC dataset contains custom programs with complex control flows, making it useful for evaluating various C features.

Coreutils. Coreutils is a widely used collection of basic file, shell, and text manipulation utilities for Unix-like operating systems, commonly found in Linux distributions. We compile version 9.5 of the Coreutils programs using musl-libc [1] with static linking, as musl-libc is lightweight and strictly conforms to the C standard. Since our lifter is designed to recover the high-level structure of binaries, we avoid using GCC extensions and remove any architecture-specific assembly code from the libraries.

From the 109 programs in the dataset, we first select 57 programs with available test cases. In particular, we check tests directory in the Coreutils repository and verify if a certain program has dedicated test suites for it. Then, we exclude any tests dependent on execution time, as performance is not the focus of our approach. We then exclude programs that rely on system calls that are not supported by our prototype, such as signal, execve, etc. After this filtering process, 37 binaries remain for evaluation. For more context, we provide the list of binaries in the table 5.

CGC. We also use the CGC dataset because it includes complex control flows, valuable for evaluating lifted code correctness, while interacting with only seven system call types. The dataset features applications of varying complexity, such as a palindrome checker, a CLI chess engine, a Flash file system emulator, an HTTP-like protocol, and a Monte Carlo simulation. It also includes POLLER, an input-output generator, which allows us to generate test cases for the binaries.

Since the CGC dataset was originally designed for a custom OS, we use the Linux port provided by GrammaTech [27] (git commit 797bd72). We statically link the math library and update its inline assembly code, replacing esp-based instructions with rsp-based ones (e.g., fldl 12(%esp) to fldl 12(%rsp)) to ensure compatibility with the x86-64 architecture targeted by our lifter.

In this version, system calls are replaced with library calls, so we implement the necessary library functions used by the CGC binaries. We collect all 247 programs from the CGC dataset, compile them, generate test cases with POLLER, and run the binaries. After filtering out 32 uncompileable, 75 untestable, and 96 test-failed programs, we are left with 44 binaries for evaluation. This is a common issue when working with CGC binaries in Linux, as the Steelix fuzzer study [36] encountered similar environment setup challenges, using only 17 binaries for their evaluation. For additional context, the list of binaries in our dataset is provided in the table 6.

9.1.2 Environment. All programs are compiled with GCC 9.4.0 using the -O0 flag. The evaluation is performed on a machine with an Intel i7-6700K CPU and 32GB RAM. We use Ghidra 11.0.3 for ILIR generation.

9.2 Expressiveness

To demonstrate that our IRs effectively represent real-world binaries, we evaluate them in two parts: validating binary execution and comparing CFG analysis with state-of-the-art tools. First, we run the lifted binaries with given inputs and verify that they produce the expected outputs without violating any assumptions. A successful execution confirms that our IRs accurately represent the binaries. Second, we compare our CFG analysis results with state-of-the-art tools. While execution provides a ground truth for validation, CFG reconstruction does not have a definitive ground truth for control flow, so we compare it to the results of existing tools.

Executing Lifted Binaries. We lift the binaries of the Coreutils and CGC datasets into our IRs and measure the validity of our assumptions. For Coreutils, we use the provided test cases, and for CGC programs, we use POLLER to generate 50 test cases.

Table 2. The number of assumption-violated binaries for ASIR and the example of the violation.

Type	# Violated		Example
	Coreutils	CGC	
Uninitialized stack	0	5	<code>int x; int y = x;</code>
Compare abstract address with concrete address	4	4	<code>if (&x < &global)</code>
Imprecise stack bound analysis	1	1	X

Table 3. The average percentage of shared nodes and edges between our lifter and state-of-the-art tools.

Lifter Pair	Shared Nodes (%)		Shared Edges (%)	
	Coreutils	CGC	Coreutils	CGC
Angr & FIBLE	94.6	95.5	64.3	65.2
BOLT & FIBLE	80.3	77.3	52.9	47.6
Angr & BOLT	79.0	74.9	44.0	38.8

For each binary, we run tests on all IRs: FGIR, ASIR, and IOIR. A binary is considered successfully lifted if it passes all test cases without violating any assumptions. For each IR, we count the successfully lifted binaries and present the results in Table 1. The results show that over 80% of Coreutils binaries and over 70% of CGC binaries are successfully lifted for all IRs, indicating that our IRs effectively represent a significant portion of both datasets.

Most assumption violations arise from abstract stack reconstruction, so we closely inspect and categorize them as shown in Table 2. The first column lists three types of violations, the second column shows the number of binaries that violate assumptions, and the third column provides examples. The first two types of violations are due to unspecified or undefined behaviors in the C standard, while the last type is related to limitations in our language design and analysis. It includes cases where the stack bounds are imprecisely analyzed, leading to incorrect assumptions about the stack layout. These issues can be addressed by improving out analysis with additional heuristics similar to real-world lifters.

CFG Reconstruction Comparison. We compare the CFGs of our lifted binaries with those of BOLT and Angr, two state-of-the-art binary optimization and analysis tools, since CFGs are a fundamental representation of binary analysis and are widely used in many tools.

Using the same binaries as in RQ1, we generate CFGs with FIBLE, BOLT, and Angr. We then measure the number of nodes whose addresses match and the number of edges whose source and destination addresses match. Different tools may handle splitting and merging nodes differently, so we normalize the CFGs by merging nodes with only one incoming and outgoing edge before comparing.

Comparing CFGs without a ground truth is inherently challenging, so we rely on previous work to compare CFGs, such as Rimsa et al. [48] and Tsang et al. [53]. They evaluate CFGs by comparing the shared and unique nodes and edges between two CFGs. We use this approach to compare the CFGs generated by our lifter, Angr, and BOLT. Specifically, we calculate the shared and unique portions of nodes and edges between our lifter and state-of-the-art lifters, averaging the percentages across binaries, where 100% represents the total combined count for all lifters.

The results are presented in Table 3. The first column lists the pairs of tools being compared, the second column shows the average percentage of shared nodes, and the third column shows the average percentage of shared edges. Our lifter shows a higher overlap than when comparing Angr

(a) Scattered plot of the lifting time and the x86-64 instruction count.

Transformation	Time Ratio (%)
ILIR \rightarrow FGIR	85.25
FGIR \rightarrow ASIR	5.19
ASIR \rightarrow IOIR	9.56

(b) Time ratio of each step of the lifting process.

Fig. 23. Time it takes to lift the binary and the ratio of each step of the lifting process.

and BOLT. This demonstrates that our CFG reconstruction closely matches the state-of-the-art tools, and that our IRs represent real-world binaries as effectively as the existing tools.

9.3 Correctness

To demonstrate that our implementation satisfies filtered-simulation, we check the simulation relations between different levels of IRs. Instead of comparing entire IR states, which is time-consuming, we focus on comparing the operands and results of operations at each execution step. To compare a concrete address in FGIR and an abstract stack addresses in ASIR/IOIR, we keep mappings between the values of the stack register for FGIR and the abstract stack addresses for ASIR/IOIR during execution.

We use the same dataset and tests as in RQ1. To check the simulation relations, we run all IRs with the same input and compare the operand values and the operation results for each execution step. As a result, we confirm that all executions satisfy the filtered-simulation for all IRs. The evaluation shows that our implementation satisfies the filtered-simulation for all given binaries, giving us confidence that the static analysis is sound and the transformation is correct.

9.4 Performance

To show that our transformations are fast enough, we measure (1) the time to lift binaries, (2) the time proportion for each stage of the lifting process, and (3) the time to reconstruct CFGs. First, we measure the time it takes to lift each binary and compare it with the instruction count of the binary. We lift a binary using FIBLE, and then count the number of x86-64 instructions in the binary by counting our constructed FGIR/ASIR/IOIR instructions. We then measure the time to lift the binary using our tool. The time is measured from the completion of Ghidra’s initialization to the end of IOIR generation, excluding the time taken for Ghidra to initialize.

Figure 23a shows the result. The x-axis is the instruction count of binaries and the y-axis is the time to lift them. The result shows that the time to lift binaries is proportional to the instruction count of the binaries. Most CGC binaries take less than 10 seconds to lift, while Coreutils binaries take around 1 minute. The longest lift time is 183.17 seconds for a binary with 1,552,747 instructions, with an average lift time of 16.27 seconds.

We also measure the time for each step of the lifting process, which is shown in Figure 23b. The first column shows the transformation and the second column shows the time ratio of each step of the lifting process. The result shows that the time to lift binaries is mostly spent on the ILIR to FGIR transformation, which amounts to 85.25% of the total time. There are two reasons: (1) the ILIR to

Table 4. Comparison of CFG reconstruction time between FIBLE and verified lifter.

Tool	Minimum Time (s)	Maximum Time (s)	Average Time (s)
FIBLE	0.10	64.99	2.98
Verbeek. et al.[55]	0.79	353.44	50.04

FGIR transformation requires fetching an instruction at a specific address, which requires Ghidra’s API, and (2) the ILIR to FGIR transformation requires a more complex analysis than the other steps.

We compare our CFG reconstruction time to the provably sound method by Verbeek et al. [55]. We ran their GitHub implementation on the same machine as ours, using the main function address as input. Although we attempted to lift the same binaries as in RQ1 and RQ2, their tool successfully lifted only 24 binaries from the CGC dataset and failed to lift any binaries from the Coreutils dataset, as it could not guarantee CFG soundness. The binaries their tool successfully lifted are marked in grey in table 6. Upon manual investigation, we found that their tool does not support binaries containing system calls, which are present in all statically linked Coreutils binaries.

Table 4 presents the results for the 24 binaries mentioned earlier. We compare the minimum, maximum, and average CFG reconstruction times between FIBLE and the verified lifter by Verbeek et al. [55]. Except for one binary, FIBLE was faster, with an average reconstruction time of 2.98 seconds, compared to 50.04 seconds for Verbeek et al.’s method. Our speedup comes from using assumptions that may not fully overapproximate the CFG, but no assumption violations have been observed in the FGIR, as shown in the previous evaluation. In summary, our transformations are efficient in the time it takes to lift binaries, which is proportional to the number of instructions. Most of the time is spent on the transformation from ILIR to FGIR, which is the most complex step in the lifting process.

10 Related Work

Static analysis techniques for binary analysis. Many researchers, including Cifuentes and Emmerik [16], Di Federico et al. [21], Bardin et al. [8], and Kinder et al. [30], have proposed static analysis techniques to reconstruct CFGs from binary code. There are relatively few works on stack frame layout analysis. Anand et al. [5, 6] proposed a technique using symbolic execution and Deshpande et al. [19] presented a technique using machine learning. Panchenko et al. [44] proposed a technique using a stack-frame information to improve the performance of binary optimization.

Our work for each analysis step is based on previous work. For example, our formulation of CFG reconstruction is similar to the work of Bardin et al. [8]. For stack frame layout analysis, we use a method similar to the work of Anand et al. [5]. One of the main contributions of this work is to combine various existing analyses with heuristic-based assumptions and to provide a formal framework to reason about the correctness of the analyses and subsequent transformations.

Formal methods for binary lifting. Verbeek et al. [55] proposed a formally verified lifting of C-compiled x86-64 binaries. They aim to provide *provably overapproximate* lifting, meaning the lifted CFG includes all possible paths in the binary without relying on assumptions, though it is more restrictive as a result. To achieve overapproximate lifting, it needs sophisticated techniques to analyze the semantics of binary code precisely. Our work does not guarantee that the assumptions used in lifting hold for all possible inputs. However, because our approach uses heuristic-based assumptions, it is more lightweight and can lift about 1,000,000 instructions in a few minutes.

Naus et al. [43] proposed a formal semantics of high-level P-Code used in Ghidra. They provide a formal semantics of the intermediate representation used in the Ghidra, but the work is more focused on the semantics of the high-level P-Code itself. Dasgupta et al. [18] proposed a scalable

validation technique of binary lifting. Their focus on validation is to ensure the instruction-level correctness of lifted code and the compositional correctness of sequences of lifted code. On the contrary, our work is more focused on the correctness between IRs with different abstraction levels.

Binary verification by abstract code. While binary lifting is a process of transforming machine code to abstract code automatically, researchers have proposed reasoning about machine code using abstract code. Myreen et al. [41, 42] proposed a technique called *Decompile-into-logic* and Verbeek et al. [54, 56] proposed a technique to build refinement relations between machine code and abstract code. Our work is similar to these work in that we reason about machine code using abstract code. The difference is that our work focuses on the automated lifting process, while their work focuses on proving the properties of machine code by the logic of abstract code. Currently, our work does not provide a verification framework for lifted code, but we leave it as future work.

11 Conclusion

Binary lifting is the process of transforming machine code to IR, and its correctness is essential for binary analysis. To provide a formal basis for binary lifting, we presented a formal framework for binary lifting based on the concept of filtered-simulation. We identified three critical steps in binary lifting and formalized the analysis and transformation required for each step: CFG reconstruction, abstract stack reconstruction, and function input/output identification. We implemented our approach for x86-64 Linux binaries and demonstrated that it can correctly lift binaries from the Coreutils and CGC datasets. Evaluation results shows that our prototype can lift about 1,000,000 instructions in a few minutes, and can lift binaries with a high success rate. Our work is a step towards a systematic approach to designing correct binary lifters, and we believe it can be extended to describe more lifter-specific transformations.

Data-Availability Statement

The artifact, including the implementation described in §8 and the resources to reproduce the evaluation results presented in §9, is available on Zenodo [45].

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A Appendix

A.1 Dataset used in Evaluation

Table 5. Description of Coreutils datasets.

Name	# Instruction	Binary size (KB)	Name	# Instruction	Binary size (KB)
basenc	22,150	138	od	26,468	160
cat	18,505	119	printf	21,784	271
chcon	25,679	156	ptx	45,937	260
chmod	24,582	150	pwd	19,285	119
chown	28,930	173	readlink	20,644	128
chroot	25,265	153	rmdir	17,261	110
cksum	51,007	271	rm	25,875	157
cp	37,041	226	runcon	16,854	109
cut	20,184	129	seq	27,771	160
df	41,145	243	shred	25,353	156
du	69,317	401	stat	46,026	260
factor	29,871	189	tac	41,771	237
fmt	19,642	124	test	24,130	146
groups	20,163	124	tr	21,178	133
head	20,009	127	truncate	18,460	118
id	22,439	138	tty	16,214	104
join	23,995	149	uniq	20,373	129
ln	25,818	162	wc	22,509	147
mv	40,505	237			

Table 6. Description of CGC datasets.
 Grey cells indicate the programs that success to lift by Verbeek et al.'s tool.

Name	# Instruction	Binary size (KB)	Name	# Instruction	Binary size (KB)
CADET_00003	668	13	KPRCA_00042	5,100	43
CROMU_00003	3,195	27	KPRCA_00043	3,632	33
CROMU_00005	2,734	22	KPRCA_00045	4,806	37
CROMU_00010	3,949	31	KPRCA_00049	4,485	37
CROMU_00058	4,775	32	NRFIN_00001	2,310	26
KPRCA_00008	3,849	29	NRFIN_00003	1,780	18
KPRCA_00011	3,926	32	NRFIN_00005	2,859	23
KPRCA_00013	7,320	46	NRFIN_00009	1,914	18
KPRCA_00014	2,977	28	NRFIN_00015	1,634	17
KPRCA_00017	3,028	28	NRFIN_00017	3,240	30
KPRCA_00018	4,676	37	NRFIN_00020	1,174	13
KPRCA_00020	3,796	32	NRFIN_00022	1,809	18
KPRCA_00021	5,022	37	NRFIN_00024	2,183	18
KPRCA_00022	3,994	37	NRFIN_00026	1,552,747	7,082
KPRCA_00023	4,662	44	NRFIN_00036	2,116	18
KPRCA_00028	4,623	33	NRFIN_00039	2,212	18
KPRCA_00030	6,401	46	NRFIN_00041	4,054	28
KPRCA_00031	5,271	42	NRFIN_00042	3,242	28
KPRCA_00033	3,987	32	NRFIN_00059	2,752	25
KPRCA_00036	5,144	37	YAN01_00007	1,977	19
KPRCA_00037	4,028	33	YAN01_00010	787	13
KPRCA_00041	4,602	37	YAN01_00012	841	15

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